

the east west divide class
solidarity privilege
antifascism fierce fight
queer anti-ableism against
power racism
no one is history
illegal beyond binary

QUEER FEMSEE

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International Conference

Queer and Feminist Studies in Eastern Europe International Conference is an interdisciplinary conference that seeks to explore various accounts of Eastern European researchers (and their Western peers with similar interests) concerning topics connected to media, cultural studies, and their intersection with gender and queer studies, all placed in the social and academic context of Eastern European countries and the Balkans.

The organizers are a group of students, researchers, artists and activists who are aware of the necessity of such events in the current socio-political context of South-Eastern Europe, Eastern Europe and beyond.

On behalf of the organizing team:

Ramona Dima (Phd candidate, Doctoral School in Communication Studies, University of Bucharest)

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Lect. Alice Iancu (The National School of Political Science and Public Administration and Hyperion University)

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ABSTRACTS & BIOS

Veronika Valkovičová

On the side of the science: scientific-knowledge use as an argumentative strategy of the 2015 Slovak “Referendum on Family”

The growing influence of „anti-gender ideology“ (AGI) groups within the Central and Eastern Europe (CEE) region also brought new reflections upon the research of gender and queer studies, as well as equality policymaking within the CEE region. The criticism of neoliberal equality policies, as well as the influence of international norm-brokers, such as the EU or international non-governmental organizations, seem to be of core and common concern of the afore mentioned groups throughout the region. Nevertheless, a number of CEE scholars such as Andrea Peto, Elzbieta Korolczuk, and Weronika Grzebalska also point to the change of the advocacy strategies within the political projects of AGI groups. According to the authors, the strategies have been recently shifting again from the „biblical“ language of morality towards the so-called scientific secularism. This, of course, is not understood as a new phenomenon within the rhetoric of faith-based advocacy groups working within the state structures, as it was denounced already by Michel Foucault within his account of the *Scientia Sexualis*. According to the current body of literature on AGI movements, science is becoming the contemporary battlefield of equality policies, as any data can be contested based on its normative assumptions. The presented article provides a discursive frame analysis of the Slovak AGI movement and its discursive strategy of framing social sciences within the 2015 Slovak National Referendum “on the protection of family”. As a number of CEE scholars accentuate, the alternative production of knowledge provided by these groups serves as a redeemed form of a discursive strategy, which puts considerable constraints on policy-making within what so many eagerly call a

“post-factual” society. Within the studied case, the AGI advocacy groups aim to present themselves as alternative knowledge producers, thus creating new realities for the Slovak equality policymaking and minority rights advocacy. The study further aims to analyze the discursive counter-strategies of the Slovak LGBTI movement in order to present a clear account of what Elsa Dorlin rather radically denounces as a new “epistemological war”.

Mgr. Veronika Valkovičová, MA is currently a joint PhD candidate at the Institute of European Studies and International Relations, Faculty of Social and Economic Sciences - Comenius University in Bratislava, and at the Faculty of Social Sciences – University of Antwerp. Within her research, she focuses on equality policymaking within the region of Central and Eastern Europe. Her dissertation is devoted to the use of numeric public policy tools within the Slovak gender equality policy. She is currently also working for a number of human rights advocacy non-governmental organizations.

David Kurkovskiy

Comparative paper on legislation and activism in Ukraine, Russia and Belarus

I propose a comparative paper that will examine the convergences and divergences of post-Soviet LGBT rights discourses and activist practices in contemporary Russia, Ukraine, and Belarus.

Such a comparative approach is useful for several reasons. First, it will give us a chance to examine the intersection of post-Soviet nation building and sexual politics, a topic which academics such as Elena Gapova have written extensively about. For example, the worsening of the official state policy toward Russia’s LGBT community might be understood through the development of a foreign policy that operates on the rejection of so-called Western

attempts at regime change. In Ukraine, discourses of Euro-integration after 2014 have led to two successful “Marches of Equality” in June 2016 and 2017, respectively, albeit not without drawbacks.

Second, this comparative approach will take into account a shared history of state homophobia that became the official policy in 1934 (with foundations in the early Soviet and late czarist years). The historical moment is an especially important one, considering that the understanding of sexual deviance and the application of the Soviet constitution to punish (mostly) male homosexuality was quite similar among the “European” republics of Ukraine, Belorussia, and Russia, as opposed to the Caucasus and Central Asian republics. While each of the three republics did not reinstate article 121 of the Soviet criminal code (the law against *muzhelozhstvo*, or men lying with men), the timeline and legal procedure of legalizing same-sex desire differed among the three post-Soviet states.

Third, this approach is conducive to a discussion of homonationalism as it can be applied to the post-Soviet context. In Russia, for example, many propagandists see the rise of publicized sexual politics as an outgrowth of Western unipolarity and foreign policy, making an “Eastern” sexual politics specially difficult to form. The use of the term “Gayropa” in Ukrainian, Belarusian, and Russian discourse, and more generally in the Russophone internet, is one such example.

Finally, the comparative approach provides a platform for a specific discussion of social organization and activist practices among the three countries. This comparison demonstrates a strong interplay between general social movements and the possibility for public LGBT organization. The crackdown on public LGBTQ demonstrations in Russia (partly a result of the nationalized anti-gay propaganda law of 2013) has resulted in activists using strategies such as satire and incorporation in general leftist street movements in the country, rather than a complete halting of pro-LGBTQ public

demonstrations (I will use Saint-Petersburg as a case study). In contrast, the limitations placed upon all forms of public demonstrations in Belarus have made pro-LGBTQ public demonstrations nearly impossible, causing activists to take to internet platforms such as Facebook and closed spaced such as art galleries. Ukraine provides a middle ground: in Kyiv, public marches have become possible (albeit with heavy police accompaniment), while L'viv and other Ukrainian cities have outright banned LGBTQ gatherings.

David Kurkovskiy is a Yale University Parker Huang Fellow, currently on a post-undergraduate research fellowship at the Kyiv-Mohyla Academy in Kyiv, Ukraine. His undergraduate studies at Yale were split between Computer Science and Russian and Eastern European Studies. In Kyiv, David focuses on the intersection of post-Soviet nation building and social movements. In particular, he is interested in the incorporation of global IT development and LGBT activism in post-Maidan Kyiv. Other interests include the digital humanities, early Soviet culture and nationalities policy, comparative (East) Slavic linguistics, and Soviet and post-Soviet LGBT history.

Mertcan Uzun

How does the heteronormative structure of a given country affect its people's attitudes towards homosexuality? Establishing a Heteronormative Typology

This paper investigates people's attitudes towards homosexuality based on the country structure they live in. It is further claimed that people's attitudes are affected by the institutionalized effects like heteronormativity that resides in the institutional organizations. It is also acknowledged that individual level characteristics are equally crucial and affect the social tolerance, therefore they have to be controlled for. One of the crucial aims of this paper is to provide an insight to the newly developing Queer Theory and the concept of heteronormativity from a quantitative perspective.

Methods

Data from 41 countries are collected to create the very first heteronormativity typology. The initial analysis is conducted based on a hierarchical cluster analysis for the establishment of this typology. Then, it is further investigated to see the effects of heteronormativity on people's varying attitudes on homosexuality based on a fixed-effect regression analysis. Main Results. It has been statistically proved that respondents living in different countries have different tolerance levels towards homosexuality, and the results are somehow expected due to the characteristics of a given country's position on the heteronormativity typology. This indicates that there is a top down institutional effect of the institutionalized heteronormativity and presumably social policies and legislations - which praise or disregard some ideas and norms, as well as individuals' personal perception. The multilevel analysis not only stresses the individual level characteristics but also the impact of living in a specific country when deciding on attitudes towards homosexuality.

Bio

I am originally from Istanbul, Turkey. With the DAAD scholarship, I have graduated from Freie Universitaet Berlin from the master programme of Sociology. My focus has always been in the areas of attitudes towards homosexuality, Queer Theory, quantitative approaches to Queer Studies, sexual orientation discrimination on the labor market. For my thesis I have worked on attitudes towards homosexuality, and established the very first 'heteronormative typology' with cluster analysis and conducting the varying attitudes with Multi Level regression analysis using STATA. I have recently graduated.

This topic of mine has been also chosen to be presented in the Conference Engendering Difference: Sexism, Power and Politics (12-13.05.2017, University of Maribor) as well as at The State of InEquality: Social Justice Under Siege that will be organized in Toronto, Canada at Humber College.

Olga Plakhotnik

The Temptation of Citizenship

In this talk, I put my recent study of feminist and LGBT+ activisms in Ukraine to the broader geotemporal framework of Eastern Europe today. I endeavor to understand how post-imperial differences are woven into the longing of activist communities for belonging to the post-colonial nation-state.

Olga Plakhotnik is a Docent in the Philosophy Department of the National Aerospace University (Kharkiv, Ukraine) and a doctoral researcher at the Open University (UK). Olga's current research interests relate to feminist studies and queer theorising: epistemologies and knowledge economies, feminist and LGBT+ activism in Ukraine and in post-socialist societies. As editors-in-chief

of a peer-reviewed open access online journal Feminist Critique: East European Journal of Feminist and Queer Studies (<http://feminist.krytyka.com/en>), Olga is keen to contribute to seminal networking between scholar-activist communities in Eastern Europe and internationally.

Crina Mureșanu **urban_roma stories reflected in photographs from the communist times**

The "Urban_roma" project is a collection of over 300 family photos selected by Crina Mureșanu from the personal archives of her family and friends, most of them living in Ferentari neighborhood in Bucharest. The photographs show Roma persons in urban environments, in familiar situations and various moments of their existence, over the generations, from the 1950s to the end of the 1980s. Thus we have an unexpected image of Roma families and persons, without stereotypes and exoticism, which are familiar, through their postures, decor or attitude, to anyone who experienced those decades.

Crina Marina Mureșanu has been working for 15 years in various civil society initiatives in Romania to promote and defend the rights of Roma minorities since 2006, focusing in particular on Roma women rights. She graduated from the Social Assistance Faculty, completed her Master's degree in Gender and Public Policy (National School of Political and Administrative Studies - Bucharest), and since 2014 she holds a PhD in Political Science. In 2008, Crina co-authored the report on (forced) Early Marriages entitled "Are Children's Rights Negotiable? The Case of Early Marriages in Roma Communities in Romania" (Romani CRISS / Unicef Romania.)

Crina has worked for the Romanian Roma Civic Alliance, and was a regional coordinator (for Romania and Republic of Moldova) of the Foundation Award for Social Integration (2010-2013), thus benefiting from relevant experience in communicating with Nongovernmental Organizations at national level and actively participating in the initiation and development of NGO networks in Romania. She is currently an expert member of the Thematic Fund for Roma Inclusion, the Swiss-Romanian Cooperation Program and is one of the founding members of the Center for Legal Studies of Human Rights where she has coordinated gender-themed projects such as: creative and recycling workshops for Roma children and teenagers, or various activities connected to the urban_roma project (such as the exhibition made in 2015 at Tranzit.ro/Bucharest). More info about this: www.urbanroma.wordpress.com.

Maja Davidovic

Women's Activism in the Eastern European "Orient": Media Representation of Eastern and South-Eastern European Women's Groups and Feminist Activists

Earlier this year on June 22nd Marcus Tanner, a British journalist, wrote about Serbia's new, openly gay Prime Minister Ana Brnabić for Balkan Insight, calling her performance of her gender as disobeying Serbian womanhood, and defying the beast-like Serbian males.¹ Immediately after, two Eastern European women were quick to, in a piece for Al Jazeera, respond critically to Mr. Tanner's clear *orientalization* of Eastern European women from his Western point

¹Marcus Tanner, "Serbia's Make-Up Free PM Shocks Me, Too" (Balkan Insight 22 June 2017) Available at: <http://www.balkaninsight.com/en/blog/serbia-s-makeup-free-pm-shocks-me-too-06-22-2017>

of view.² In 1985, Margaret Atwood wrote about a dystopian world where certain women became the *Unwomen* for resisting patriarchy.³ This paper aims to take this concept an *Unwoman* – one that does not deserve to call herself a woman, at least not the way the male oppressors want her to perform her gender, and explore its becoming in the context of Eastern and South-Eastern European (SEE) women. Applying the notion of intersectionality, this paper wishes to particularly focus on women activists and self-declared feminists, including both grassroots women’s groups like FEMEN, blamed for being “too much” of a woman, and individual female politicians like Brnabić, blamed for being “not enough” female. Through the lens of orientalism, this piece will elaborate on the representation of such women’s groups by media sources that have the Western authority, and could be deemed neocolonial. As a part of the methodology, the article will analyze written contributions published shortly after “unwomanly” events (e.g. protests), adopting Derrida’s notion of *phallogocentrism*, according to which the written word, and meanings attached to it are gendered and subject to patriarchy, too.⁴ Some of the questions this paper, therefore, will ask are the following: what groups and individuals are seen as *Unwomen* by the Western media? Who has the authority to criticize Eastern and SEE women’s womanhood? How do Western women approach these performances of gender unheard of in Eastern Europe? If essentializing, sensationalizing, and scolding is detected, what are the consequences of such practices for the future development of Eastern and SEE feminism?

² Marija Pantelic and Lana Pasic, “On make-up, Serbian women and a lesbian PM” (Al Jazeera 29 June 2017) Available at: <http://www.aljazeera.com/indepth/opinion/2017/06/serbian-women-lesbian-pm-170629101526315.html>

³See: Margaret Atwood, *The Handmaid’s Tale* (Anchor Books 1998, first published in 1985).

⁴See: Jacques Derrida, *Writing and Difference* (Chicago: The University of Chicago Press 1998).

What the paper aims to achieve is twofold. Firstly, this research aspires to add to the important, yet underdeveloped discussion about neo-colonialism and racism in and towards the former socialist countries, and point out to the subordination and simplification of women (and men alike) from this region that persists to date. Secondly, through discussions about media (mis)representations of Eastern and SEE women activists by female authors as well, this paper wishes to prove the existence of double standards towards feminism. More precisely, it is the authority of Western women (and men) to direct the struggles of Eastern European women who therefore diminish as independent authors, and are thought of more as objects, that this paper is interested in.

Maja Davidovic is an independent researcher from Serbia. She is a recent graduate of the Human Rights master's program at the Legal Studies Department at Central European University in Budapest, Hungary. Her research interests include transitional justice, gender justice, international criminal law and child protection, and she has written and published on women's rights and racial issues in her home country, as well as on international criminal justice. Her MA thesis explores women's activism before international human rights bodies in enforced disappearances cases, and looks for traces of gender sensitivity in awarding redress. Besides academic research, Maja has also worked with different NGOs in the Balkans and Turkey on issues related to child protection and disaster relief.

Laura Sandu

Tractor-Driving Women: Socialist Realist Depictions of Women in 1950s Romania

Since I first declared my interest in studying women representations in Romanian painting of the 1950s, I have frequently been asked (often with a condescending smile on the side), both by scholars and people outside of the university: „Oh, so you want to write about those tractor-driving women?”

In Romanian arts history, „socialist realism” describes mostly the art of the first twenty years of the socialist regime (Cârnelci 2000) and points to the regulation of the artistic practices, with the aim to support, complete and reflect the regime’s political project of producing, along with a new social order, a new subjectivity.

Much like some of the regional research dealing with the subject (Kivimaa 2010, Sachs 1995, Toniak 2008, Bonnell 1991), this essay aims to outline some of the specifics of local realist socialist representation of women. Because though some of the most visible post-communist comments (Popescu 2009, Petre 1998) understand these depictions in terms of „distorting” femininity, the 1950s paintings and the texts that support and surround them tell a different story, one that calls for a more complex perspective.

An essentialist take on gender defines both the official art discourse of the 1950s and the post-communist underlying frame of analysis.

Perhaps surprisingly, the archives show the traditional traits of the artistic representation of female subjects are not completely lost in the socialist realist translation (grace and maternal predisposition, for example, are ruminated upon by critics, as they praise portraits of women workers). The representations of women as revolutionary heroines, factory workers, farmers or authority figures, are far from engaging in a glorious display of female masculinity (nothing like the work of Soviet painter A.N.Samokhvalov, for example). However, they do include women in the political project of

subjectivity production in a quite dignifying way (unlike the traditionally praised Romanian art that until recently had represented women in the objectifying manner of Aman, Grigorescu, Pallady, Iser).

In light of these facts, we can ask at least two questions:

1. Is there anything to reclaim in these representations, from a non-essentialist position, or, because of the context of their production, and of the present readings, they obstinately resist such initiatives?

2. What is so memorable about the artistic representation of a tractor-driving woman? In the Romanian realist socialist iconography, the portraits of tractor drivers are not that common. Most of those asking me about this do not really remember where they have seen it. Yet, this image became an epitome of „the masculinized working class woman (...), one of the most ridiculed signifiers of the Soviet regime and especially of its gender ideology.” (Kivimaa 2010). Why does it have such a potential for ridicule and how can we respond with joyful feminist thinking?

Perhaps focusing on the tractor driving woman will tell us more about the present than the past. Our socialist past is still locked in rigid formulas, that swiftly point to its repressive, authoritarian, heteronormative character, dictating that nothing valuable could possibly come out of it.

However, it just may be that when revisiting the socialist realist depictions of women, with a non-essentialist perspective on gender (E.Grosz, J.Butler, J.J.Halberstam) and from a point of view informed by affect theory (S.Ahmed, R.Braidotti), these images might just unlock their potential to challenge not only local essentialist and heteronormative narratives, but also the mainstream understanding of our recent past.

Laura Sandu is a PhD student at the Center of Excellence in Image Study, University of Bucharest, where she is finalizing her thesis on the representation of women in Romanian socialist realist painting. Over the past 10 years, she has worked as a translator, copy editor, writer, trainer. She is part of several informal groups where, together with her friends and colleagues, she contributes to the collective developing of a lived local feminist perspective, drawing on intersectionality, queer theory, post- and decolonial theories, socialist feminism.

Kseniia Semykina

Media construction of LGBT prides in Russia: who are the ones to frame?

Several aspects of LGBT movement in Russia make it an exceptional research case. First, its agenda was decriminalized only in 1993, when previously adopted legal norm punishing male homosexuality was repealed. Secondly, the incentive for the recent development of the movement was the discussion of laws prohibiting “public propaganda of homosexuality”, the process that started in 2006 on the regional level. [1] As social movements are dependent on the media in communicating ideas to the public, it is important to study the movement’s representation in the media. Framing theory has been widely used for such analysis. It views the media as an arena in which groups of interest promote their frames, or interpretations of the discussed issue. [2] Frames juxtapose elements of the text in such a way as to provide the audience with a scheme audience to perceive the message. [3] Social movements are viewed as a group of interest that introduces new frames in the public deliberation. Some hypotheses on representation of Russian LGBT movement can be made. First, under coverage of the rallies could be present, as the movement proposes ideas that may threaten the legitimacy of laws.

Secondly, the movement's representation is expected to follow the logic of criminal chronicle. As Gitlin discovered, protest groups with claims opposing official discourse may be marginalized in this way. [4] Thirdly, religious leaders could play an active role in the public discussion of LGBT prides as they traditionally participate in discussions on homosexuality. The study focuses on articles dedicated to Saint Petersburg LGBT prides in years 2010-2014 in the most popular local Internet websites. Following Entman's definition of frame, interpretation of the issue, its causes, moral judgments and remedies are identified. [5] Inconsonance with van Dijk's model of news discourse, actors participating in the discussion, their characteristics and expert commentary are analyzed. [6] The analysis shows that LGBT prides are commonly represented as the struggle for civil rights, and not as homosexuality propaganda. Religious activists' interpretation of events is present in the media, but it does not dominate in the discourse. Moreover, prides involving bans and arrests are covered by the media more actively than those without any incidents.

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- 6) van Dijk, T.A. *News as Discourse* / Hillsdale, NJ: Erlbaum, 1988.

Kseniia Semykina graduated with a double degree from Saint Petersburg State University, Russia and Bard College, US as a Bachelor of Arts and Sciences and starts her Master's studies at Higher School of Economics, Moscow, in autumn 2017. Her academic interests include media studies, frame analysis, gender studies. In 2015, Kseniia completed an internship at the Coalition for Civil Equality "Together", an LGBT organization in Saint Petersburg. The same year she participated in a workshop "LGBT researchers and activists: points of cooperation" in Saint Petersburg. In 2016-2017, Kseniia presented reports at a number of conferences in major universities of Moscow and Saint Petersburg. Her research paper on representation of gay marriage in Russian media won first prize in a contest held by Higher School of Economics and was awarded a finalist status in a contest by a nation-wide sociological center VTsIOM.

Lemonia Gianniri

Gender and sexualities in media. Layers of discrimination, representations and examples of good practices in Greece

Media representations tend to reflect upon the predominant heteronormative culture and impact the construction of subjectivities, socialities and stereotypes. Thus, gender and sexuality representations in mass media is a crucial topic in the sphere of queer-feminist discourse, since they can illuminate discriminations, generalizations, and reinforce biases. However, considering the power of the image and television, good practices of representations, with realistic, fully-realized characters, can shape and structure views towards more inclusive and emancipated societies. Focusing on gender and sexuality representations in Eastern European countries is imperative, precisely because of the scarce examples of good

practices along with the lack of situated and systematic research on the topic. This paper deals with gender and sexuality representations in Greek Television. Greek television, produced from and addressed to Greek society, is a vital tool to examine given representations, situate them on the cultural aspect and document the few examples of good practices. The term “good practices” in this paper is being used to describe realistic, multidimensional characters who struggle and enjoy as the rest of the characters, and their sexuality is not being ignored or silenced, under the patriarchal and heteronormative cultural hegemony. The three examples that this paper examines, Billy in “Iperoxa Plasmata” (Kontova, 2007), Pavlos and Giorgos in “Kleise ta matia” (Papakaliatis, 2003) and Vicky and Katerina in “Dio meres mono” (Papakaliatis, 2005), entail queer representations within the modern patriarchal Greek society, and thus create a space for further discussion upon gender and sexuality expression when projected in mass media of a south-eastern European country. In particular, the three different paradigms offer interesting insight in the complexity of considerable representation of queer desire in Greek television. Billy is a gay journalist that lives in Athens as one of the three main characters of *Iperoxa Plasmata* (amazing creatures), along with his two female best friends. This dramedy underlines the affection and caring among these friends while they reflect upon ways of relating. Pavlos, struggles with his sexuality and his desire to be with Giorgos who was in a relationship with a woman until he met him. They are not the main characters of the drama series “*Kleise ta matia*”, yet they form big part of the plot. The next series of Papakaliatis, *Dio meres mono*, hosted the first lesbian couple, Vicky and Katerina, who are raising a child together. Nonetheless, the child is perceived as a product of infidelity, returning to the banal ideal of heterosexual reproduction and monogamous stereotypes (Kouskoumvekaki, 2007). Invoking the work of feminist film critic Laura Mulvey and the idea of the male gaze, Sara Ahmed’s queer methodology (2006), Ann Cvetkovich’s writing on mass media and

sexualities, along with Berger's media analysis techniques (1998) and the collaborative work "Queer Methods and Methodologies Intersecting Queer Theories and Social Science Research" (Brown, Nash, 2010) this paper aims to frame the aforesaid given examples of good practices within the queer feminist discourse, in order to examine the possibilities and "impossibilities" of queer representations when applied in the specific regional context.

Bio

I am a social scientist based in London. Born and raised in Athens, Greece, I have a degree in Psychology from the National and Kapodistrian University of Athens. My final project was a qualitative research titled "views of young male homosexuals in Greece: the world from both sides". Since 2015 I reside in London, where I graduated with distinction from the MA Psychosocial Studies at Birkbeck college. My dissertation was focused on gender and homosocial representation on some of Samuel Beckett's texts, titled "Absurd subjectivities: A psychosocial reading of Homosocial, Gender and masculinity representations in Waiting for Godot, Endgame and Mercier and Camier". In 2017, I was awarded with the UCL, Bloomsbury & East London Doctoral Training Partnership, from the Economic and Social Research Council (fees only) to continue my studies at a PhD level. My main research interests are: sexuality studies and theories, queer and feminist theories, gender representations, subjectivity production, psychoanalysis and culture, theatre.

Stefan Žarić

***Queering the Academia and (Re)fashioning the (Sub)culture:
Visual Analysis of the Gay Bear Culture***

Given the hybridization of academia and expansive interdisciplinarity in the recent years, an urge to requestion disciplines conceptualized in socialist discourse common for Eastern Europe emerges. Such discipline is art history, which is „suffering“ a positive influence from disciplines like fashion and queer studies, among many. The proposed paper hence aims to analyze visual identity of a queer culture through means of art historical and fashion studies analysis, and moreover, to queer classically conceptualized art historical discipline. By following the historical formation of the gay bear culture from its sub-cultural initiation to the mainstream presence, the author aims to bring visibility to queer phenomena in Serbian / Eastern European academic discourse, and destabilize heteronormative notions of these academies. Since its initial appearance in the 60s, the bear (sub)culture leaned to great extent on visual aspects while proclaiming its identity. Speaking of the present moment dominated by visual communications, the bear culture completely bases its identity on the visual. As such, the bear culture is not only socio-cultural phenomena, but a visual one as well, which enables it (and many other queercultures) to be inscribed in canons of art history, visual anthropology, fashion studies, and visual/popular culture studies respectfully, and not only within socio-cultural anthropology, gender, and queer studies frameworks. Given the specific chromatic choices of the bear pride flag, iconographic elements like a bear paw, and conscious selection of material culture (fashion, clothes, accessories, especially on the examples of fashion designers Walter Van Beirendonck and Costello/Tagliapietra) in its identity, the bear culture holds a potential to be examined through methodological frameworks of art history and fashion studies. Besides opening the new chapters in

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national/regional humanities, the author will as well tackle issues of intersectionality and internalized homophobia, and how analyzed visual codes were first used to distinguish bears from both hetero and homonormativity, while today are imposing it upon other gay cultures, considering them less masculine in regard to the bear culture. Additional attention will be paid to the potential reading of the bear culture on regional level.

Stefan Zaric (Žarić, b. 1991) is at graduate student in History of Modern Art, University of Belgrade, Serbia, with a focus on fashion history and intercultural exchange between the West and Serbia/Eastern Europe. During his BA in Comparative Literature and Art History in Serbia, Stefan spent an exchange year at the University of Minnesota, USA, under The US Department of State scholarship, where he interned as a student guide and researcher in the field of modern American art at Weisman Art Museum. As a queer individual, Stefan was one of the initiators and coordinators of the University's Drop in center for international LGBTQ students, aiming to provide aid and consulting for international non-western students facing crises of expression in liberal environment. After completing his program in the USA, Stefan co-curated several fashion themed exhibits in Serbia, and successfully enrolled himself into graduate school. His MA thesis, exploring influences of Western, dominantly American fashion and pop culture on Serbian art, is in the process of being published and turned into an exhibit, with Stefan being curator in charge. In addition to studying in Serbia and the USA, Stefan spent a research semester as Erasmus+ scholar at the University of Tartu, Estonia, at the department of Semiotics of Culture and Art, and interned as a curator of design exhibit at the Tartu Art Museum. He is the project manager of Curated Couture, an online independent platform aiming to promote and develop fashion studies in Serbia. Stefan holds fluency in Serbian and English, and satisfying knowledge of French and Russian.

Greg Stepniak

Old Is The New Queer: Perspectives On Aging in the New Polish Cinema

Using Jack Halberstam's theory of queer time and place as a framing device, this paper considers the process of aging and makes an attempt to show its queer implications. Referring to the temporal and spatial turn in the field of Queer Studies, directed at analyzing modes of being in the world that are not necessarily linked to the models of (homo)sexuality, the main objective is to present the non-normative aspects of old age that derive from its supposed non-productivity and „uselessness.” Considering these cultural stereotypes, we perceive the elderly as not only improper citizens, but also what Dean Spade calls „illegal subjects”. Paradoxically, in the face of rapidly progressing aging of the Western societies, a radical reconfiguration and reformulation of the old paradigms and ideas around aging are of greater importance than ever. The latest Polish cinema and its representations of aging can help us consider the particular theoretical and social context in which this paper considers aging. Agnieszka Holland's movie „Spoor”, awarded at this year's Berlinale, has been described by the director as an „eco-anarcho-feminist thriller,” and it is centered around an aging woman living in a small village, close to the Czech border, who decides to take revenge on the men responsible for killing her beloved dogs. What could be seen as character's strangeness and weirdness, together with her status as a social outcast and pariah, precisely because of her age, is shown in this article as a source of subversive power, yet also – extreme vulnerability, as defined by Sarah Schulman. The queer, feminist utopia from the finale of the film is next confronted with an extreme dystopian, yet very much naturalistic portrayal of an aging woman in Tomasz Wasilewski's picture „United States of Love”, awarded at Berlinale last year. By

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contrasting this very film that tells the story of four women struggling to survive in a small Polish town in the early 90's, one of them being a closeted lesbian, with Holland's strong, however straight-identifying female character, the author suggests that it is not sexuality per se that queers the representation of the old age, but more its relation to the time, space and cultural norms around it.

Greg Stepniak holds a PhD in the Humanities, his dissertation is centered around queer implications of childhood, adulthood and old age in the American performance art and cinema. He graduated from Theatre Studies, Drama Studies and finished a dramaturgy course at the Theatre Institute in Warsaw. He studied at Pittsburgh University, at UCLA School of Theatre, Film and Television and University of Southern California, Los Angeles. He publishes articles in various magazines and journals, including "bi weekly" and "Didaskalia. Theatre Journal" and also translates films and academic articles. Stepniak is an assistant professor at the Department of Media and Cultural Studies at the University of Pedagogics in Cracow. He also works as a Senior Programmer of NETIA OFF CAMERA International Festival of Independent Cinema and collaborates with Divine Comedy Theatre Festival. His academic research is focused on Gender and Queer Studies, Race Studies and American film, theatre, television and performance art.

Justyna Struzik & Agnieszka Król (co-author Joanna Mizielińska)
Queer kinship, queer aging – perspectives from Poland

The proposed paper analyses the narratives of older gay and lesbian people living in same-sex relationships, gathered during focus groups interviews conducted in 2015 within “Families of Choice in Poland” research project led by Joanna Mizielińska (2013-2016). The main theoretical framework applied in the study, namely “doing family”, sheds light on practices and every-day experiences of doing queer kinship. The analysis brings together issues related to coming out strategies and visibility, caring practices and defining a family, as well as experiences of exclusion and visions of political and social change. The experiences and identities of the older gay and lesbian people often elude the contemporary understanding of gay, bisexual and lesbian identity, primarily since they avoid labeling their relationships in an explicit way. The contemporary LGBTQ culture is often centered around youth and thus marginalizes experiences and needs of older LGBT people. The narratives of older gay, bisexual and lesbian people reveal and reflect complex shifts and processes taking place in post-socialist countries in the last few decades. The identities as well as experiences of this group are embedded both in the past regime denying an existence of homosexuality and current social context, still characterized by homophobia, yet bringing the development of LGBT organizations and movements.

Our paper will focus emerging needs of older LGBT people regarding care. The lesbian voices differ from gay narratives in respect to fear of being frail and ill. While older men underline their agency regarding preparing themselves for being old or sick (e.g. by organizing informal care facilities in advance), older lesbians primarily describe their anxiety of being a burden to their partners or family members. We will draw on defining and negotiating queer

kinship by older gay men and lesbians, who frame their experiences by referring to intimacy and close friendship.

Joanna Mizielińska – she holds DSs (habilitation) in sociology, University of Warsaw and a PhD in Women’s Philosophy, Institute of Philosophy and Sociology of Polish Academy of Sciences. She currently works as an Associate Professor at the Institute of Psychology of the Polish Academy of Sciences. Her interests concentrate on queer theory and sociology of gender, sexuality and families. Her past research centred on the politics of translation of Anglo-American queer theoretical approaches/concepts into other geo-political contexts and the question of exclusion. Her current research focuses on queer kinship and queer families. Recently she was a Principal Investigator of the project “Families of Choice in Poland” (2013-2016) which was the first multi-method project on non-heterosexual families in Poland. Currently she is a Co-Investigator in the research project “Queer(y)ing Kinship in the Baltic Region” [dir. by prof. U. Dahl, Södertörn University, Stockholm]. She is the author of *Different or Ordinary? Families of Choice in Poland* (2017), *Sex/Body/Sexuality* (2007) and *(De)Constructions of Femininity* (2004) and co-author of *In different voices. Families of Choice in Poland* (2017) and *Families of choice in Poland. Family life of nonheterosexual persons* (2015). She is co-editor of *De-Centring Western Sexualities: Central and Eastern European Perspective* (Ashgate, 2011). Her most recent writing focuses on critical analysis of discourses on families of choice in Poland (*Journal of Homosexuality*, 2017) and doing research on queer kinship beyond Western queer paradigms (*Sexualities*, 2017). Currently she writes a book on familial and parental practices of families of choice in Poland.

Website: familiesofchoice.pl

Justyna Struzik - has received her PhD in sociology from the Institute of Sociology at Jagiellonian University in Cracow, with the thesis “Queer Movements in Poland”. Currently she is a Postdoctoral researcher in the project “Disentangling European HIV/AIDS Policies: Activism, Citizenship and Health”. Her research interests are social movements, sexuality, gender. Co-author of the book *In Different Voices. Families of Choice in Poland*.

Agnieszka Król – sociologist, PhD candidate at Jagiellonian University in Cracow. She has been involved in several research projects on gender, social exclusion and LGBT rights. Currently she writes her dissertation on reproductive justice and disabilities. Co-author of the book *In Different Voices. Families of Choice in Poland*.

Dorottya Rédei

Reproducing intersectional subjectivities and social inequalities through sexuality in schooling

In this paper I focus on intersectional subjectivity constitution and social inequality reproduction in secondary education and discuss how class and ethnicity are reproduced through gendered sexuality discourses and practices on the institutional level of the school. The data I use for the analysis come from a school ethnography which I conducted for my doctoral dissertation between 2009 and 2011 in a combined secondary vocational-technical-grammar school in a large town in Hungary. The school had approximately 1000 students, who were mostly coming from lower-middle-class and working-class backgrounds and were ethnically mixed, i.e. there was a significant proportion of Roma students. My fieldwork consisted of observing sex education and other lessons, semi-structured small-group interviews with 90 students and individual interviews with the school

nurse, 5 teachers and the school director. The sexuality discourses and practices I have identified and the subjectivities they constitute simultaneously create categories of exclusion and allocate people within and outside, leading to a re-inscription of social inequalities in schooling. After a brief introduction of the educational profile, the student and teacher population and the hierarchical structure of the school, I apply critical discourse analysis on interview excerpts with students and teachers to show how axes of social inequality get constituted intersectionally through sexuality discourses, and especially how ethnicity, gender and class converge to create student and teacher subjectivities. I discuss some challenges I was facing when doing intersectional analysis involving more than two analytical categories (class, race/ethnicity, gender, sexuality), and the particular challenges in attempting to use 'class' as an analytical category in a post-socialist context where the notion of 'class' is not employed or it is reduced to refer to 'socio-economic differences', ignoring the cultural aspects of class. Similarly, I will briefly reflect on the use of 'race' vs. 'ethnicity' in the specific context of an ethnically monolithic post-socialist society with one significant ethnic minority (Roma people). I argue that gendered discourses on sexuality in this school constitute binary categories of race/ethnicity and class, and contribute to the formation of students' subjectivities based on these categories. In other words, sexuality is not only one of the axes of social inequality, it is also constitutive of these axes.

Dorottya Rédei received her PhD in Gender Studies in 2015 at Central European University, Budapest. Her dissertation, "Sexing the School. Constituting Gender, Ethnicity and Class through Discourses of Sexuality in a Hungarian Secondary School" focuses on the intersectional subjectivity constitution and reproduction of social inequalities through sexuality in an educational institution. Currently she is working at CEU in international projects in the field of gender and education. Besides her academic work, she has been involved as

an activist in the work of Labrisz Lesbian Association and several feminist and LGBTQ NGOs in Hungary, mainly working on educational, research, community-building and awareness-raising projects.

Rita Béres-Deák

Same-sex parenting practices in Hungary as an assertion of intimate citizenship

Intimate citizenship, in Plummer's definition, focuses on the possibility of decisions, access and choices related to the body and intimacy (Plummer 2003). Though some authors limit the use of this framework to sexuality and thus make it coterminous with sexual citizenship (e.g. Bell and Binnie 2000), it is in fact broader and may include practices like choice of family form. Though Plummer (2003) emphasizes the agency inherent in intimate citizenship, other authors tend to focus on structural inequalities that constrain it for certain groups (e.g. Chateauvert 2008), so members of these groups become second-class citizens (Bell and Binnie 2000) or even non-citizens (Phelan 2001). This second strategy, however, constructs people with non-normative sexualities as passive victims; therefore, we need to acknowledge both social constraints on intimate citizenship and individual or community strategies for overcoming these.

In Hungary the law severely curtails same-sex couples' possibilities to become parents: they have no access to joint outside adoption, second-parent adoption, surrogacy or assisted reproduction technologies. Under these circumstances, non-heterosexuals wishing to become parents use various strategies and tactics (de Certeau 1984) to circumvent the system. Based on ethnographic fieldwork in the Hungarian LGBTQ community (including interviews, participant observation and analysis of online forums and blogs) I will examine

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some of these from an intimate citizenship perspective. I argue that while some such tactics – like activist lobbying for parenting rights (Bell and Binnie 2000) – are widely acknowledged in literature as forms of asserting intimate citizenship, there are other, less often discussed tactics (like breaking the law or leaving the country) which are also proof of same-sex couples' agency and claim to equality. With this analysis I aim to contribute to a more nuanced understanding of intimate citizenship and practices related to it in the post-socialist region.

Rita Béres-Deák (January 10, 1971-) is a cultural anthropologist and LGBTQ activist in Hungary. She received her BA in Cultural Anthropology at ELTE Budapest University in 2001 and her MA in Gender Studies at the Central European University in 2002. She received her PhD also from the Department of Gender Studies at the Central European University in 2016, with her dissertation topic focusing on the relationship between same-sex couples and their family of origin. In the winter term of 2017 she taught a course at the same department on Family, Gender and Sexuality. Her main research interest is LGBTQ communities, but she has also done research on gender representations and people with disabilities. She is actively involved in LGBTQ activism.

Nicole Butterfield

Imagined Rural/Regional Spaces:

Non-normative Sexualities in Small Towns and Rural Communities in Croatia

This research aims to critically examine how the complexity of the ongoing process of “coming out” and the narratives of LGBTQ individuals who live in or come from small towns and rural spaces in Croatia undermine the imagined hierarchical distinction between rural/urban and larger regional spaces. Based on interviews with gays, lesbians, bisexuals and queer/non-identifying individuals who come from or currently live in small towns and villages in Croatia, I argue that their experiences subvert imaginaries of their communities as homogeneously hostile and threatening. Some participants did, however, perceive other spaces, on a regional and national scale, as either “gay-friendly” or “deep homophobic”, reflecting both local and transnational discourses of “uneven sexual development” to use Marlon Ross' term (2005). As Croatia is transnationally perceived to be a part of a larger “homophobic region”, the construction of the rural/urban hierarchical distinction is (re)produced and (re)configured within discourses that signify Western countries and so-called more developed regions within Croatia in comparison as “more open and liberal” as opposed to “more homophobic and backward” spaces. I will discuss how these distinctions between countries, regions, and the rural/urban spaces come into contradiction with each other and are undermined by my interviewees' own incongruous experiences.

Notes:

1. Ross, M. B. (2005). Beyond the Closet as Raceless Paradigm. In E. P. Johnson & M. G. Henderson (Ed

Bio

I am currently an independent scholar who is an affiliated member of the Gender Studies Research Group at the University of Szeged. I recently completed a one-year, post-doctoral research as part of the NEWFELPRO Fellowship Programme in Croatia at the Department of Ethnology and Cultural Anthropology, University of Zagreb. Previously, I was a lecturer at the English Department in the Institute of English and American Studies at the University of Szeged, Hungary from 2012-2015. I was also a Visiting Lecturer at the Gender Studies Department, Central European University, Hungary, in the academic year 2014-2015. I successfully defended my dissertation titled, "LGBTIQ Advocacy at the Intersection of Transnational and Local Discourses on Human Rights and Citizenship in Croatia" and received my PhD from the Gender Studies Department at Central European University in 2014. My current research interests include (sexual) identity politics, theories of human rights, transnational NGO-ization, neoliberalization in post-socialist contexts, and rural sexualities.

Prof. Judit Takács (Institute of Sociology, Centre for Social Sciences. Hungarian Academy of Sciences - IS CSS HAS)
Disciplining (homo)sexuality in the state-socialist era

Despite the growing interests in contemporary LGBTQ+ politics in the “Eastern Bloc” (i.e. state-socialist countries in the period between 1945 and 1990) as well as the ongoing historicizing of life under socialism, “homosexual politics” and state-socialism are rarely examined together. From the 1960s in an increasing number of Eastern Bloc countries the totalitarian state control was replaced by a milder form of authoritarian control that left some, at least not directly controlled, space for private life. Nevertheless the particular lived realities of state-socialism, namely, state surveillance, the lack of private space, along with a deep-seated homophobia played a crucial role in shaping the lives of people in East-Central Europe. In my presentation I will provide a historical contextualization and some illustrations of *queer life behind the Iron Curtain* on the basis of mainly Hungarian archive material and in-depth interviews with people who lived through that experience.

Judit Takács (born 1968) is a Hungarian sociologist, researcher and university professor. She is a Research Chair of the Hungarian Academy of Sciences and works at the Institute of Sociology of the Centre for Social Sciences. Her main research interests are family roles, work-life balance, social history of sexual minorities, transphobia, homophobia, discrimination, equality, HIV/AIDS prevention.

Tomasz Basiuk

The Queer 1970s in Poland as a Proto-Political Time

I will present some preliminary findings from an ongoing study of Polish queer history of the 1970s. (The study is part of a HERA-funded project “Cruising the 1970s: Unearthing Pre-HIV Queer Sexual Cultures.”) Based on oral history interviews and other sources, I will argue that there was virtually no sense of a politically motivated homosexual identity in Poland up until the 1970s although some institutions for social and sexual contact persisted, in a limited scope, from the interwar years. The absence of criminalization cut down on state-sponsored persecution of homosexuality but tacit homophobia nonetheless prevailed, resulting in a near erasure of homosexuality from public discourse and making it difficult to call oneself queer (lesbian, homosexual, etc.). But the Seventies also saw a rise in economic prosperity and in opportunities for international travel, and some remaining prohibitions on homosexuality had been relaxed, e.g., male prostitution was decriminalized at the cusp of the decade. One central process taking place with respect to queer culture(s) of the period was the growing visibility of queers, including for and among themselves, with queers self-organizing as informal groups without a political agenda. The other was a greater ease of cultural transfers, both within the Eastern block and between Poland and the West, including knowledge transfers in sexology. Rudimentary forms of social self-organizing, occurring in a granular fashion, aided by reinvigorated cultural transfers, preceded and arguably enabled a sense of a politically motivated identity emerging in the second half of the 1980s, laying the ground for overt activism in the late 1980s and the 1990s. Much more is known about these later decades, whereas the 1970s, a crucial transitional period, remain under-researched. The study I am describing addresses this deficiency. In making this argument I will reference Douglas Crimp’s

notion of “queer before gay,” developed in his discussion of the New York sexual and artistic scenes of the 1960s. I will also call on provisional figures of visibility drawn by Samuel R. Delany in his autobiography *The Motion of Light in Water* and his discussion of urban spaces in *Times Square Red, Times Square Blue*.

Tomasz Basiuk holds a doctoral degree from the University of Warsaw and a post-doc degree (habilitation) from the University of Gdansk. He teaches queer studies in an American Studies program at the University of Warsaw. For the past year, he has been Principal Investigator in a HERA-funded project “Cruising the 1970s: Unearthing Pre-HIV Queer Sexual Cultures,” which focuses on Poland and three other European countries. He has published extensively on queer studies, including the monograph *Exposures: American Gay Men’s Lifewriting since Stonewall* (2013). He co-edited three volumes of papers on queer studies and is a founding editor of *InterAlia*, a queer studies journal (www.interalia.org.pl).

Franko Dota

The Yugoslav Socialist Debate on Decriminalization of Male Homosexuality in the 1970s

Out of two hundred (mainly Western European) delegates that convened for The Congress of the International Association of Penal Law in 1964 in The Hague, a large majority voted for a resolution advising national governments to decriminalize consensual same-sex relations. Representatives from socialist Yugoslavia, where “unnatural fornication” was – as in many other European countries of the time – still a criminal offence, strongly supported the idea and presented one of the main papers in favour of decriminalization of homosexuality. This example alone indicates how the persistent post-1989 narrative of a sharp divide in the treatment of

homosexuality between the communist East and the liberal West does not pass the test of new historical evidence. Following the demise of state socialism in Europe, many elements of the anti-communist Cold War propaganda that successfully survived in popular perceptions, as well as in historiographical narratives. One such element was a widespread belief that the East was intrinsically sexophobic, asexual or even antisexual, a place where erotic pleasures were supposedly constantly subjected to political intrusions, control and repression. This image is part of a master-narrative that depicts the socialist experience as inherently anti-individualistic and illiberal. R. Kulpa and J. Mizielińska (2011) challenged this deeply rooted East-West sexual dichotomy. They demonstrated how this "hegemonic temporality of West" is presented as continuous and linear, progressive and accumulative, even when it displays strong repressive and conservative tendencies.

On the other hand, as is my intention to argue, similar phenomena in communist biopolitics are habitually depicted as static, eternally burdened with traditionalism, patriarchy and homonegativity, and therefore old, backward and irrational. In these narratives the sexual history of the East is represented as a failed or unfinished modernization. However, new methodological approaches and histories of sex and sexuality of Eastern Europe indicate that the narrative of a deep divide between a repressive and sexophobic communist East and a supposedly liberal and dynamic West is untenable.

The presentation will try to show how different legal and medical debates on decriminalization in socialist Yugoslavia were linked to similar discussions elsewhere in Europe, both East and West. Yugoslav sexologists and lawyers were well acquainted with and quoted extensively Magnus Hirschfeld, the Kinsey Reports, the Wolfenden Report, Hans Giese's books and the American Model Penal Code. When the question of decriminalization was brought to the attention of the legislator, all its proponents, together with the

mainstream press, formulated a final and crucial argument: almost every European country had done it, so if it wants to keep its progressive image on the world stage, Yugoslavia must follow in their footsteps as soon as possible.

The paper will be based on an extensive archival research, as well as on an analysis of public debates on decriminalization in the 1970s Croatian and Serbian press. The main theoretical approach follows a comparative transnational perspective in a *longue durée* historical framework.

Franko Dota recently submitted his PhD dissertation on the legal and medical history of homosexuality in socialist Yugoslavia at the Department of History, Faculty of Humanities and Social Sciences in Zagreb, where he previously obtained his MA in History and in Italian language and literature. He taught courses on contemporary history at the Faculty of Humanities in Rijeka. He is the author of *Zaraćeno poraće: konfliktni i konkurentski narativi o stradavanju i iseljavanju Talijana Istre* (Srednja Europa, Zagreb, 2010) [Post-war History at War: Narratives on Persecutions and Migrations of Italians from Istria]. He is active in the Croatian LGBT movement and was among the founding members of Zagreb Pride organization.

Anna Borgos

***“For thirty years I lived as if I didn’t have any gender.”
Views and experiences of gender subjectivity by lesbian
women in state socialist Hungary***

My paper explores the personal experiences and social representations of lesbianism in Hungary during the Kádárera, based on sixteen elderly women’s interviews of the “Secret Years” oral history project, and on contemporary written psychiatric, sociographic and social history sources on female homosexuality. My analysis focuses on how the interviewees’ thinking about lesbianism, relationships, gender, motherhood and family reflected contemporary (“lay” and “expert”) public ideals and discourse on these issues. I also explore whether their lesbian identity itself influenced their concepts about womanhood and gender, or their relationship to feminism and women’s movement.

During the political consolidation of the 1960s and the soft dictatorship of the 1970s-80s, under Kádár’s policy of “tolerance, prohibition, and support,” lesbian women’s existence and meeting places were “tolerated”, but they lived a highly closeted life. “Proper sexuality” was an important mediating area for the ideals and ideologies of gender roles, the monogamous family, and the socialist society in general. The personal stories in the interviews reveal the direct or indirect influences of the social-political environment of the era on private life, as well as the hidden or semi-public spaces where women were able to meet. Coming from diverse social and economic backgrounds, they have different perceptions of their situation, but express similar experiences of repressing an important layer of their identities and personal lives as lesbians.

The interviews present a unique perspective on recent Hungarian social history through personal lenses, and provide material for reflecting on the adequacy of Western concepts of ‘public’ and

‘private’ in the specific context of state-socialist Eastern Europe. The interviews also give insight to women’s approach to and concepts on femininity and gendered subjectivities. They represent different views, ideals, and understandings of what it means to be a woman and it is informative regarding how being a lesbian affects their notions and performances of gender. Deviating from the “mainstream” usually involves struggles and inner conflicts, but it may also open paths towards new and autonomous self-definitions and relations to social norms.

Anna Borgos is a psychologist and women’s historian, a research fellow of the Institute of Cognitive Neuroscience and Psychology of the Hungarian Academy of Sciences, and a founding member of Labrisz Lesbian Association. Her latest book, *Nemek között. Nő történet, szexualitástörténet* (Between the Sexes. Women’s History, Sexuality-History) came out in 2013.

She also co-edited a volume of lesbian autobiographical writings, *Előhívott önarcképek* (Developed Self-Portraits) and a volume of interviews with elderly Hungarian lesbians, *Eltitkolt évek* (Secret Years). With Judit Takács, she co-edited a special issue of the Journal of Lesbian Studies in 2011 (“Voicing Women from Eastern Europe”).

Maria Irod

Representations of Male Homosexuality in Romanian Autobiographical Literature: Ion Negoïtescu, Mihai Rădulescu and Petre Sirin

This paper intends to analyze the lives and works of three Romanian male authors whose works were published posthumously after the collapse of Ceaușescu's dictatorial regime in 1989. Ion Negoïtescu (1921-1993), Mihai Rădulescu (1919-1959) and Petre Sirin (1926-2003) explored homosexual and masculine identity in their autobiographical works, set in the complex historical context of elite intellectual circles in the interwar and communist period. Through attention to the intersectional oppressions faced differently by each of these three authors in socio-political context, this paper understands itself as a contribution to the nascent field of Romanian gay/queer literary and cultural studies.

Maria Irod, PhD in German studies at the University of Bucharest, Assoc. Professor of German literature at the "Dimitrie Cantemir" Christian University, Bucharest; literary translator "Stefan Odobleja" fellow at the New Europe College, Bucharest 2016-2017 Research interests: Austrian contemporary fiction, German speaking literature in Romania and South-Eastern Europe, gender and queer theories, discourse analysis, religious studies, especially the intersection of gender/sexuality, religion and literature.

Magda Szcześniak (Institute of Polish Culture, University of Warsaw)

Queering Post-socialism – Notes on Dispersed Archives

Most probably, the first coming out ever witnessed by Polish TV viewers was performed by a fictional character—Steven Carrington from the US series *Dynasty*. The words „I am gay,” translated into Polish, were repeated several times in a tear-jerking scene, the dramatic effect rendered stronger by extreme close-ups and long pauses. The episode aired in 1990, nearly a decade after its original premiere. And yet—despite its belatedness—in Poland the scene must have come as a shock, the topic of homosexuality remaining taboo. On one hand, the appearance of a gay character could be considered revolutionary, and is—by some LGBT activists in Poland—mentioned as a breakthrough moment. On the other, the ephemerality of such an event makes it incredibly difficult to gauge its meaning and importance. What was its effect? Could it have even been registered by the millions of Polish *Dynasty* devotees, most of whom have never met or seen a gay person?

Departing from this example, my presentation will seek to present the methodological difficulties of writing the history of Polish queer. This archive, an archive „without an official home”—consisting of little-known, obscure zines (such as the first Polish gay-zine „Filo”, started in 1986, but also other gay magazines, published in the 1990’s); homophobic articles from the mainstream press; photographs from secret drag queen and cross-dressing sessions; documentations of first, unsuccessful attempts of breaking into the public sphere—is one which demands close and patient reading and which resists being modeled into easy, linear narratives of progress. While analyzing its potentialities, I will try to show how a queer archive demands a queer method of investigation. One of the most inspiring examples of such an approach is the work of young Polish

visual artist Karol Radziszewski, whose films, magazines and installations not only investigate the queer structures of the past, but also test their political potential today.

Magda Szcześniak, Ph.D. – Assistant Professor in the Section for Film and Visual Culture, Institute of Polish Culture, University of Warsaw. Her main fields of interest are visual culture, post-socialism, class theory, gender and queer theory. Author of book *Normy widzialności. Tożsamość w czasach transformacji* [Norms of Visuality. Identity in Times of Transition] (Warsaw 2016) and of numerous articles in Polish academic journals. In 2010, she received a Fulbright Foundation Junior Advanced Research Grant and spent a year at the University of Rochester in the framework of the Graduate Program for Visual and Cultural Studies. Recipient of the National Science Center „Preludium” grant (2013-2015). Winner of the 2017 “Polityka” Academic Award. Co-creator and editorial team member of the academic journal “View. Theories and Practices of Visual Culture” (pismowidok.org).

Daniel Alexandrov

#PRIDE – the first Bulgarian LGBTI play

The paper presents the theater play “#PRIDE”, created in Bulgaria. “#PRIDE” is a documentary theater play, which uses the verbatim technique to tell the stories of participants in Sofia’s first Pride in 2008; it is the first Bulgarian LGBTI+ play of its kind. The paper also explores the situation in the artistic sphere, theatre in particular, and its relation to the LGBTI+ community in the country; it places “#PRIDE” in the current context of the development of that community and the history of the movement in Bulgaria, noting in detail the first Sofia Pride. The paper presents and discusses the use of the verbatim technique, as a method in the documentary arts field,

and its socially-engaging role. The verbatim technique allows actors to directly listen to the voices of actual people and convey them on stage. The stories in “#PRIDE” have been taken and recorded through interviews with participants in the first Sofia Pride, as well as people separately related to the event. Furthermore, the paper explains the aims, process, realization, results, and effects of the project. Initially, the idea behind “#PRIDE” was to create a Bulgarian theater play that gives visibility to LGBTI+ problems; to commemorate the achievement of the less than 80 people, among whom heterosexual as well, who have overcome their fears to publicly support the idea for a Pride; and also, to engage, introduce, provoke people outside the LGBTI+ community with these topics. “#PRIDE” was first staged on May 24, 2016 and it celebrated its 10th play on June 8, 2017, when the photography exhibition of first Prides from around the world “#PRIDE #1 – THE FACES OF THE BRAVE” was shown, to mark the anniversary of the project.

Daniel Alexandrov is an activist from Sofia, Bulgaria, born in 1993. He practices Philosophy with Children and Philosophical Counseling. He has graduated as a Bachelor in Philosophy in 2017 from Sofia University “St. Kliment Ohridski”. The topic of his thesis paper (to be published) is “The problem as an ontological aspect of Philosophical Counseling”. Daniel is the author of the documentary theater play “#PRIDE”, created in May, 2016, and co-organizer of the photography exhibition “#PRIDE #1 – THE FACES OF THE BRAVE”, first shown in June, 2017. He is the creator of “The Bulgarian Queer Archive” – a project that will be presented in late 2017, which aims to document LGBTI+ history in Bulgaria.

Derya Acuner & Adil Serhan Şahin
Diva of Self-Legitimation

Bülent Ersoy, ‘the older sister’, or ‘the Diva’ is a rather controversial figure in Turkey ever since the launch of her career in the mid 1970s. What makes this then classicist, later to turn to arabesque [music] singer and musician popular is rather unique in the contemporary Turkish social, cultural and political lives. Ersoy, a male to female transsexual by all means carved her existence in the minds of the Turkish nation at home and abroad. Her “queerness” or with other words her very existence became the centre of attention of even parliamentary debates in the midst of the coup d'etat in 12 September 1980 and even after (she was banned to perform in Turkey for eight years and even served jail time prior the coup). Yet, throughout her career, Ersoy is rather well-known for another attribute; this being her unparalleled talent of self-legitimation in a seemingly conservative, muslim society. Her self-legitimation even caused Ersoy’s male to female transsexual status a distant event in the past or rather a ‘correction’ in her life. This surprising construct of self is the centre of this paper as well as legitimation throughout a career spanning more than four decades. In this article we aim to focus on three turning points in Ersoy’s career, all of which are consumable items or products of the media industry. We aim to start with her movie entitled as ‘Şöhretin Sonu/Yüzkarası - End of Fame/Disgrace’ (1981), a dashing queer treasure of Turkish cinema, her televised speech against war on ‘Popstar Alaturka’ (a musical talent show in which she was one of the judges) broadcasted live on 24 February 2008 which led yet another judicial process and finally her “performance” during the recent television series of ‘Dünya Güzellerim (My Most Beautifuls)’ [localised version of the international reality TV Show Grandpas over Flowers, South Korea or Better Late than Never, USA]. These three turning points,

respectively took place in 1981, 2007 and 2017, all intersect with important social and political crises mark also moments of self-legitimation and queer performances. This paper will focus on those three aforementioned turning points in chronological order and methodologically analyse each moment, will summarise the background atmosphere and analyse the outcome(s) while getting closer to present day. Desktop research, newspaper and audio-visual as well as web archives will be heavily relied on for pinpointing those exact moments of Ersoy's self-legitimation will be used. By analysing those moments of self-legitimation and analysing the queerness of them, we hope to seize a moment in the contemporary Turkish history where, queerness, patriarchy, gender binary, hegemony, popular culture and finally political turmoil fight or took advantage of each other individually or as a group.

Derya Acuner earned her Master's degree in Cultural Management from Istanbul Bilgi University. She currently works at Women for Women's Human Rights - New Ways, one of the renowned feminist NGOs in Turkey. Her major fields of interest are herstory, women's experiences in urban areas, and modern Turkish history from a feminist perspective.

Adil Serhan Şahin is a Ph.D. candidate in Communication Studies at Istanbul Bilgi University, he also works at the same university as a Research Assistant at the Department of Arts and Cultural Management, Faculty of Communication for five years. His research interest is focusing on masculinities, trans-men and gender.

Mima Simić

Humor as tool for activist seductions: from game shows to referendums

LGBT+ rights movement, more than any other, has depended on the visibility of its protagonists – and coming out has been its greatest tool. Although the states formed following the violent break-up of Yugoslavia have tried to fix their "new" identities around (heteropatriarchal and religious) tradition, with its pro-capitalist practices and agenda, the postcommunist public arena has also provided new spaces for queering the nation-state. For over a decade now, as a writer, media/film critic and an activist, I have been trying to harness popular formats (quiz shows, cooking shows, talk shows, documentary films, women's magazines, etc.) to promote lesbian visibility and unleash the political potential of the (seemingly) non-political (pop)cultural formats. Avoiding the familiar (victim, trauma) narratives that commonly go with LGBT+ existence, I have managed to both subvert the purpose of these highly capitalist media products (entertainment) and raise lesbian visibility in a country where silence and (self)censorship are still the rule of the day; particularly in the light of the neo-conservative wave that is washing over the whole of Europe.

What I propose is not a paper (although I could do that, too) – I propose a 60-minute performance with slides and video-clips of my media interventions and alternative/creative approaches to doing LGBT+ visibility (for instance, in 2016 in the course of 12 weeks I drove 16,000 km across the U.S. interviewing people of marginal identities living on the geographical margins; probing the East/West dichotomy and stereotypes about sexuality, geography, identities). I will talk about the importance of creativity in activism, as the ultimate formula for life-long activist duration, about detecting the unsuspecting spaces and audiences, and finding the right language

for them.

As a writer and a critic, I see all communication as seduction – particularly when it comes to politics – and I believe storytelling and humor to be its most potent devices. Thus, my presentations often resemble stand-up performances – with a lot of anecdotal and informative material, regularly accompanied by in-depth analysis of the context and implications. I believe this could be an interesting, exciting and inspiring addition to the conference.

Mima Simić is a Croatian writer, film and media critic and political activist. She holds degrees in English Language and Literature and Comparative Literature from the University of Zagreb, and an MA in Gender Studies from the CEU. Her short stories and critical essays have been published in numerous Croatian and international publications. In 2009 she was named the best Croatian film critic. In 2011 she was named the Croatian LGBT person of the decade. In 2016 she received the OSIFE Effective Activist Fellowship. She lives between Zagreb and Berlin, and she loves cats more than life itself.

Francesca Romana Recchia Luciani & Ethan Bonali
Femininity as a cisheteropatriarchal imposed concept: dialogue around the contribution of non-binary identities and feminism in the path of emancipation through body and sexuality

Femininity is a cisheteropatriarch, imposed set of socially constructed attributes and behaviors that seems to come from its relationship with masculinity, rather than as a consequence of its own features.

This model involves the whole feminine spectrum determining social and legal boundaries and including feminine body chiseling and women sexuality behavior and desire naturalisation based on mere

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biological fact related to reproduction and on men's narrative and expectations.

The trans body is no exception; cisheteropatriarchal transition therapies access criteria, identified in the 1960s, such as passing and gender role compliance, are still valid in many countries, including Italy and Eastern Europe and it's a system of domination that enforces the application of a binary where none exists.

Trans women body, unable to procreate, was designed as a sexual fetish, by imposing a sexuality entirely responsive to the patriarchal imagery and removing the reality of the male organ by bringing trans women to suppress their ability to enjoy pleasure and laying the groundwork for exclusion from the lesbian world.

The struggle of trans-women for orgasm is, sexually, the continuation of the struggle of feminist emancipation and, at the same time, the beginning of the deconstruction of heteronormative sex in which non-binary identities are involved.

The collapse of gender binary sexual equilibrium leads to genders contaminations and new gender boundaries negotiation out of the penetration logic based gender classification, and involving feminist issues by filling the artificially constructed sexual gap between man and woman.

Gender spectrum becomes fluid and negotiable.

The work will develop a dialogue between feminisms and non-binary and queer identities starting from Carla Lonzi thought in "Donna vaginale e donna clitoridea", using Julia Serano's concepts of oppositional and traditional sexism as mentioned in her chapter of Whipping Girl titled "Putting the Feminine Back into Feminism", to the much more recently Jean-Luc Nancy in his latest book, Sexistence (2017) and ending with non binary bodies and sex experiences.

While avoiding any use of ontology to explain the meaning of the sexuated existence of each human being, the goal of this work is to focus on the centrality of sexual relationships and practices in the

experience of living individual and how much sex leads to a transformation of life subject.

Francesca R. Recchia Luciani, Ph.D.

Associate Professor of History of Philosophy University of Bari "Aldo Moro" - ITALY University of Bari (Department of Humanities).

Associate Professor of Contemporary Philosophies Core Research and Teaching Faculty Program in History of Contemporary Philosophy, Human Rights, Gender and Women's Studies 2005 – present.

Continuous teaching in:

- Philosophies and Epistemologies of the twentieth and twenty-first century
- Philosophy in Arts and Media
- Human Rights, Women and Gender studies

Founder and scientific coordinator of Women and Gender Studies Festival sponsored by the Interdepartmental Center of Studies on Gender Culture of the University of Bari "Aldo Moro" from 2012 to date on yearly basis.

Founder and scientific coordinator of the Course of History and Teaching of the Holocaust sponsored by the University of Bari "Aldo Moro" from 2013 to date on yearly basis.

Founder and scientific coordinator of the Short Master in Theory and Didactic of the Rights of Differences. Feminism and Gender Studies sponsored by the University of Bari "Aldo Moro" from 2016 to date on yearly basis.

Ethan Bonali, 39, non-binary transgender man, queer activist, blogger, model, engineerarchitect, cultural heritage researcher, and catastrophic event operator.

Volunteer in the 2012 Emilia Romagna earthquake and in 2016 in Marche and Umbria earthquake.

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He lived in Brazil for a year in an ex-favela of Sao Paulo where he has been able to observe the transgender community and develop his studies regarding emergency and border architecture.

Winner of literary competitions, author of the blog "Abbatto i Muri", Pasionaria, Gaypost and cofounder of "Non-binary Italy" blog.

Conference and activism: He recently participated at the "3rd International Day in Gender Studies, The Feminine in the Italian and Portuguese Language" with the work entitled "The Contribution of Queer Culture in Dance between Construction and Deconstruction of the Genus in Italy and in the Lusophonic Countries".

He participated at the 2017 edition of the "Festival delle donne e dei saperi di genere" in the section "Militant Writings" and presented the lecture "Desire and Power: Dance as a Principle of Recognition and Identification Between Choreography and Social Scenography" and now he's part of the organization board of the 2018 edition of the festival.

Member of the Intersexioni Board, Intersex and Transgender Rights Activist Group.

Main Research Interests:

queer in architecture, study of arts (especially dance) as a instrument of construction and deconstruction gender, hate speech and dynamics of narcissism in the transgender world, nonbinary and non-conforming gender identity, gender self-determination of transgender people, gender creative children, sex work and intersectional feminism.

Joanna Sieracka

Provincializing Postfeminism. Postfeminist Art in Poland

The notion of postfeminism has not been invented in a vacuum. It is deep rooted in the Western feminist academic discourse, which, as Samuel Nowak indicates, “has been developed synchronously with changes of Western societies” (2011). What characterizes such a context is strong influence of second wave feminism and – according to Angela McRobbie – its “transformation into a form of Gramscian common sense” (2009). Moreover, references to feminism (“taking it into account”, as McRobbie puts it) and its achievements is what is typical of postfeminist discourse.

Thus, uncritical implementation of the category of postfeminism into the Polish context may raise many doubts. Poland’s convoluted history resulted in specific gender relations. Because of long lack of sovereignty, ambiguous relations between the private and the public, scarcity economy and professional activation of women in the Polish People’s Republic as well as a short history of democracy, application of Western feminist chronology and conceptual framework is difficult.

As a result, the term “postfeminism” appears very rarely in both public debate and academia in Poland. However there is one exception: art critique and academic discourse on art. The term “postfeminist” is often applied to the visual arts, in particular these made by women after 2000. Postfeminist art in Poland is characterized by irony and self-irony, subversiveness, focus on performativity and fluidity of gender and sexuality, usage of materials traditionally associated with women, narcissism, individualistic values and narratives, affirmation of traditional female roles, girlhood and immaturity, emphasis on pleasure and refusal of political commitment. The latter feature, as well as “the break with the poetics of blood and nakedness” (Raczek 2005), puts this artistic

trend in opposition to the critical art from nineties.

In my paper I would like to trace the ways in which the category of postfeminism functions in discourse of art and art critique. I also aim at unpacking its ideological background and implications. My goal is to decide, whether such a category is relevant in Polish context. I would like to find out, whether it is already provincialized, translated and adjusted to the specificity of local context, and if so – to indicate, to what extent postfeminism in Polish art is different from the one characterized by McRobbie (2004, 2009), Genz (2009), Gill (2007), Negra and Tasker (2007). To this aim I would like to define its local specificity and answer the following questions:

To what extent does the opposition between critical art and postfeminist art influence the meaning of postfeminism?

Is there any feminist tradition which postfeminist art in Poland refers to? Or perhaps we have to do with “postfeminism without feminism”?

What is the relationship between postfeminist art and other spheres of social and cultural reality? Why is the term “postfeminism” overrepresented in artistic discourse and hardly ever applied to the other realms of culture and society?

What are the political consequences of postfeminist artistic “refusal of political commitment”? Is postfeminist art in Poland still feminist?

Joanna Sieracka is a PhD candidate at the Institute of Cultural Studies, University of Wrocław, Poland. Her current research focuses on the issue of cultural specificity of postfeminism in Poland.

Aia Beraia

Nationalism and Hegemonic Masculinity in Post-Soviet Georgia

Nationalism and nation state are modern phenomena which are closely related to modern masculinities. Nation state as an institutional power system is intertwined with hegemonic masculinity. In post-Soviet Georgia the creation and development of neoliberal nation state was accompanied by various types of nationalism and hegemonic masculinity. In addition, considering post-Soviet/postcolonial specificity in Georgia, it is possible to distinguish two types of nationalism, which I call anti-imperialist nationalism and pro-Western nationalism. The theoretical framework is based on Connell's theory of masculinities, Gramsci's concept of cultural and political hegemony and Nagel and Reeser connecting hegemonic nationalism and hegemonic masculinity. The research aim is to study interrelation, intersection and tendencies of nationalism and hegemonic masculinity in post-Soviet Georgia. The objectives focus on studying the ideas of nation and masculinity in the discourse of political and economic elite, analysis of anti-imperialist and pro-Western nationalism and studying how national Other is constructed. The study is done from queer and postcolonial feminist standpoint. The methodology is drawn up by combining feminist epistemology and the theoretical and methodological approach of critical discourse analysis (CDA). Research method applied is critical discourse analysis as well, while analysed data was selected from public speeches, statements, articles and interviews of the elites. One of the main findings of the study is that the ideas of nation and masculinity are generated simultaneously, also there are three major types of hegemonic masculinity as a construct. The research also reveals the prevalence of anti-imperialist nationalism, although it is often combined with pro-Western

nationalism. The domination of this latter type throughout the history can be interpreted in two ways.

Bio

I am a Georgian feminist and queer activist. I have the degree of bachelor in political science. I am graduating from Gender Studies MA in Tbilisi. My research interests include: gender and nationalism, gender and global politics, masculinity studies, queer studies. I mainly work from queer and postcolonial standpoint.

Malgorzata Kot

Catching up with the West or constructing own path? Discourses and strategies on LGBT families in Poland

What are the interactions of West (here understood as Western Europe and America) and CEE regarding LGBT activism, particularly in the field of LGBT families? I regard Kulpa's and Mizielińska's graph of geotemporal Western and Eastern temporalities within LGBT movements particularly useful, as it attempts to explain differences in strategies of LGBT groups in these regions. Currently it is difficult to discuss nonheterosexual histories without references to Western discourses, which only shows how the flow of knowledge and concepts dominated Central Eastern European thinking. Practically, what it means for LGBT activism in CEE is the never-ending attempt to catch up with the West; the attempt which will never succeed as CEE will always lag behind. As paradoxical as such an attempt might seem, it keeps Western hegemony and as a model to follow and sustains the division 'us'/'the Other'. Robert Kulpa in his article on Western leveraged pedagogy of Central and Eastern Europe shows on the example of three EP resolutions on homophobia how this division is used in policies.

Homophobia is depicted as a particular issue of Poland and CEE member states, strengthening the image of Western Europe as progressive and caring for equality (Kulpa 2013). The LGBTI equality is measured by the organization with the usage of Rainbow Europe, the index where the presence or absence of specific legal solutions constitutes the place at the beginning or end of the list (ILGA-Europe 2017). By bringing this example, I wouldn't like to undermine the importance of protection of LGBT community by specific laws. What I'd like to highlight is the importance of critical approach to such measurement tools. Among the policies mentioned in the index, the laws on marriage equality, registered partnership and joint adoption are included as equality indicators. Questions which arise when looking at these specific indicators are the following: does the equality mean necessarily having solutions associated with heteronormative rules (family, marriage)? And aren't such legal solutions the way to normalize, therefore assimilate LGBT persons instead of applying queer strategies? Such questions raise doubt in the linear development of Western LGBT strategies as assimilation/integration and queer strategies are both utilized. Such approach might be helpful in questioning the stability of framing Western LGBT movements as critically different from CEE ones. Linear development of LGBT movement where assimilation stage is the past doesn't prove to be necessarily true; only the goals differ but method which aim for acceptance of the heteronormative majority remain similar. Still, the direction of LGBT movement relying on recognition of same-sex relationships, families made by same-sex couples or marriage equality seems to be embraced by CEE countries as well. What language is used when discussing and acting for LGBT families (if they are called like this) and what strategies are used? In this paper I will particularly focus on Poland to observe the flow and usage of Western concepts and strategies in Polish media and NGOs discourse on families created and sustained by nonheterosexual persons; I'll also refer to the wider context of CEE

to discuss research on LGBT families conducted in the region.

Kulpa R. (2014) Western leveraged pedagogy of Central and Eastern Europe: discourses of homophobia, tolerance, and nationhood in: *Gender, Place & Culture: A Journal of Feminist Geography*, 21:4, p.431-448.

Kulpa R. and Mizelińska J.(eds.) (2011), *De-Centring Western Sexualities: Central and Eastern European Perspectives*, Ashgate. ILGA-Europe, Rainbow Europe 2017, <https://www.rainbow-europe.org> [accessed 27th June 2017].

Małgorzata Kot, PhD candidate in sociology at the Graduate School for Social Research at the Institute of Philosophy and Sociology of the Polish Academy of Sciences. She's interested in queer theories, nonheteronormative kinships and families. Her doctoral thesis is focused on mothering among nonheteronormative female couples in Poland.

Masha Neufeld & Katharina Wiedlack

Visibility, violence and vulnerability: lesbians stuck between the post-Soviet closet and the Western media spectacle

What makes people subjects of solidarity? What kind of visibility is necessary to get recognition? Is recognition necessary for solidarity? In our presentation we want to take up all these questions to ask about the privileges and hegemonies of solidarity in connection to lesbians coming from the post-Soviet space to Western Europe and the US. We want to discuss the invisibility of violence that they face, especially when it comes to the current questions about migration and refugees. The topic of (homo)sexuality has been in the focus of both Russian as well as Western discourses on Russia since about 2012. Western media proliferated a so far unseen amount of pictures

and reports of queer/LGBT activism and harassment in Russia, starting with the introduction of the first so called “anti-homosexual propaganda law” in St. Petersburg in 2012 until today. Reports, videos and photos narrated stories about the Russian homophobia and queer/LGBT dissidence and activism.

Our presentation questions these narratives of Russian queer/LGBT and raises questions of who becomes represented; which actors, which bodies and which forms of activism become visible within predominantly western media, and which ones are overlooked and deprived of Western solidarity? Since the law was named the “gay propaganda law” by the Russian media and the term “gay” (“гей”) defines only a male homosexual individual in Russian language, most of the official homophobic media narratives were focused on gay men. Therefore, lesbians, bisexuals and to some extent trans* people became subjects that are unidentified by the society and can to some extent escape the disciplining power of the state and embody some alternative lifestyles and strategies of the opposition to homophobic initiatives. Often dismissed as “being in the closet”, these not (at least entirely) openly lesbian lifestyles, however, can be also considered as forms of silent resistance, self-preservation and self-care, especially when it comes to lesbian community building in the form of friendship circles and hang-outs, the so called “tusovka”. Still, the discursive invisibility of lesbians in Russian speaking contexts also leads to the underestimation of female and non-binary activists’ work, the underrating of the aggression that they face and the lack of political awareness and reasons for solidarity among LBTQ that are not professional activists. We argue that in both discursive fields—international media as well as activism—only physical violence against gay (cis-)men becomes visible due to its value as a media spectacle, while the physical as well as structural violence against lesbians, trans*people and women is much less frequently addressed. This lack of representation and understanding of discrimination and violence that lesbians face in Russia and other

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post-Soviet countries leads to the situation where they are not taken seriously in their needs, which can prove to be fatal, especially when we considers the situation of lesbian asylum seekers in Europe.

Masha Neufeld holds a diploma degree in psychology and works on her PhD project on the topic of alcohol consumption and health in Russia at the Institute of Clinical Psychology and Psychotherapy at TU Dresden and the Institute for Mental Health Policy Research, at the Centre for Addiction and Mental Health, Toronto. As an activist, queer scholar and life-long migrant she is part of several multilingual research, artist and activist collectives and networks and has been organizing queer-feminist events in Vienna, Berlin and Novosibirsk on a regular basis. She is founder and coordinator of the Siberian Queer-Feminist Initiative and the cultural association "Планета №9".

Dr. Katharina Wiedlack is a post-doc Research Fellow at the department for English and American Studies, University of Vienna and visiting scholar at the Center for Advanced Media Studies, Johns Hopkins University. She has conducted research and lectured in the fields of Cultural, Gender, Queer and Disability Studies at the University of Berkley, Yale, University of Vienna, State Technical University Novosibirsk and other universities, and she was writer in residence at the Jordan Center, New York University during 2015/2016. Her most recent research project focuses on the sexualized, gendered and racialized representations of Russian bodies in US media and the construction of US national identity.

Slaven Crnić

A Return Ticket? East, West, and the Travelling Queer Literary Studies

Literature was always one of queer theory's main interests, not least because a number of its central arguments were first formulated in literary departments, and many of its best-known concepts – queer itself included – were defined and refined through textual analysis. As evidenced by a growing number of contemporary literary studies that bear the prefix “queer” in its title (e.g. Fantina 2006; Calvin 2008; Furneaux 2009; Bibler 2009; Cusset 2011; Furneaux 2011; Mehl 2012; De Villiers 2012), contemporary Western queer research on literature is alive and well. Drawing upon the work of pioneering authors such as Michel Foucault, Judith Butler, and especially Eve Kosofsky Sedgwick, all these projects are closely knit together by their theoretical background and complementary methodologies.

These developments in queer literary studies coincided with the emergence of different, yet mutually informed studies of the culture and society of socialist Yugoslavia. A number of these analyzed gendered and sexual aspects of Yugoslav society and culture (among others, Kuhar 2003; Dimitrijević 2008; Jovanović 2012; Dota 2017). Taking part in a wider, emerging and ongoing wave of contemporary research on Yugoslav culture in general, queer research appears in a variety of disciplines, and uses diverse methodologies and theoretical frameworks. However, queer inquiries into socialist period literary production remain scarce (especially when compared to the much more developed queer approaches to, for instance, Yugoslav cinema), and queer interpretations or findings predominantly appear as a corollary to a different central issue.

This presentation will argue in favor of an interpretative turn that would elevate queerness from an incidental and sporadic object of curiosity to the very center of literary interpretation. By making

queerness a crucial impetus behind literary analysis, rather than its corollary, the presentation will address two theoretical and methodological issues. Firstly, I will try to map out the conceptual trajectories of both implicit and explicit usages of queerness in post/Yugoslav cultural and literary studies. Although the concepts and the eponymous theory did not originate in Yugoslavia, I want to eschew and emphatically argue against the notion of a simple “application” of “Western queer theory”. As a number of genealogies of queer theory show, it would be hard – and, indeed, very un-queer – to argue that a monolithic set of issues invariably governs queer theory and activism in various parts of the world or that there has to be an established field of gay and lesbian studies as a precondition for queer theory. Outside US, queer theory and activism were shown to have many different trajectories, appearing alongside and sometimes even before gay and lesbian studies and identity politics, to which they are often contrasted, exemplifying that queer theory is a “travelling theory” (Said 1983; also Mizelińska 2006; Cusset 2008; Dioli 2009; Lim 2009; Dahl 2011; O’Rourke 2011). Secondly, the presentation will make the case for queer literary studies of novelistic production in socialist Yugoslavia as part and parcel of the region’s longstanding tradition of feminist thinking on gender and sexuality (more in Slapšak, Blagojević and Kolozova 2006; Dojčinović-Nešić 2006; Lóránd 2015).

Slaven Crnić is a PhD student in Comparative Gender Studies at the Central European University in Budapest. His research focuses on representations of male homosociality and queerness in novelistic production from the period of socialist Yugoslavia. He holds an MA in Cultural Studies. He has taught at the Department of Cultural Studies at the Faculty of Humanities and Social Sciences in Rijeka, and Center for Women’s Studies in Zagreb. He is a founding member of the Center for Women’s Studies at the University of Rijeka.

Vanya Solovey

“Global Standards” and “Internalized Coloniality”: What Russian Feminists Think of “The West”

The “Western” gaze on queer and feminist subjects in postsocialist spaces has been shown to be objectifying, erase difference, and re_produce clichés—one common example, especially when it comes to activists, is to construct them as heroic victims of a conservative majority and/or a repressive government. While critical discussions of the “Western”-centric discourses on feminism in Eastern Europe have been both important and necessary, I believe that approach to be insufficient. Focusing on dominant discourses, even if done critically, still has the paradoxical effect of strengthening them. Instead, I suggest de-centering the “Western” perspective by examining the “East”/“West” relationship from an “Eastern” point of view: what do Russian feminists think of “Western” ones? In what capacity are “Western” feminist theories and/or movements interesting or relevant for Russian feminists? Do they need a dialogue with “Western” activists or researchers?

To answer those questions, I draw on my current empirical research on contemporary feminist movements in Russia. My general theoretical vantage point is shaped by feminist intersectional, post- and decolonial theories, as well as critical postsocialist studies. However, I use the constructivist grounded theory method to prevent my analysis falling back too easily on extant theories and prioritize instead careful work with empirical data. My research focuses on grassroots feminist movements and scenes in several Russian cities. Their participants are people who live on the intersection of several discriminations, including class, sexual and gender identity, race, age, dis/ability, etc., and are mostly involved in activist projects aiming at consolidating local communities. Those Russian feminists have little in common with “Western” clichés, and “Western”

sympathizers generally know nothing of their politics, struggles, or achievements.

Russian feminists, for their part, cannot afford not knowing what has been going on in “Western” feminism. Some think of the “West” as a model of progress and of “Western” feminist movements as setting the “global standards” that Russia needs to try and catch up with. Others are extremely critical of the “Western” cultural hegemony, while simultaneously opposing even more decisively the nationalism promoted by Russian elites. In my presentation I will examine closely the range of Russian feminist perspectives on “the West” and discuss the functions each of those perspectives fulfills for Russian feminist movements and movement discourses. I will also raise the question of what those perspectives’ sheer multiplicity can tell about the relationship between “Western” and Russian feminisms and about the possibility of a dialogue between them.

Vanya Solovey grew up in Moscow and was active there in various feminist and lesbian initiatives. He currently lives in Berlin and works on his doctoral dissertation at the Center for Transdisciplinary Gender Studies, Humboldt University.

Rahel Katalin Turai

The role of queer, heteronormative and progressive straight community spaces in experiences of non-heterosexuality in Budapest

In a post-socialist city like Budapest, a diversity of sexual-political-cultural positions plays out on the level of community spaces. Whereas homonormative groups like Catholic communities are aligned with the ruling right and with a critique of what are seen as ‘Western values’, LGBTQ spaces, actively engaged with the latter, provide shelter and affirmation for non-heterosexual

identities. People with same-sex desires in Budapest are also welcome in several predominantly straight communities like musical subcultures and academic spheres, which define themselves as in opposition to the conservative right. My paper examines the role that these three types of spaces play in personal experiences of changing sexuality, and I will show that they all provide a strong sense of belonging, which produces conflict in people's sexual and other identities to various extents.

I thus argue that the operation of these spaces illuminates the specificity of the region in the global hierarchies with a strengthening gay discourse which is identified as Western. I suggest re-thinking queer temporality as deconstructing developmental ideas on both the personal and the geographical level. To this end, I use the framework of critical post-socialist

studies of sexuality (Woodcock 2004, Kašić 2005, Kulpa and Mizilińska 2011, Stella 2014, Bilić 2016), which draws attention to sexuality as key in the discourses on/in Central-Eastern Europe as backward, nationalist, or sovereign. I combine its insights with those of critical bisexuality studies (Hemmings 2002, Eisner 2013), which suggest a post-structuralist view of sexual subjectivity as fragmented and examine its changes and multiplicities in light of the specific social context.

I provide a deep narrative analysis of 10 life story interviews I made, which contain experiences with how queer and straight communities relate to the same person's hetero- and homosexual desires. I suggest that a strong emphasis on stable identities characterizes all groups, which poses difficulties in identification for some even in the progressive spaces. I propose to examine the temporality of sexual experience as in close relation to its spatiality, thus introducing 'transition' as a key term of queer temporality which builds post-socialist tensions into our understanding of sexual fluidity.

Ráhel Katalin Turai is a doctoral candidate at Central European University, Budapest in Comparative Gender Studies, submitting her dissertation 'Sexual Transitions: Biographical Bisexuality in Post-Socialist Hungary' in October 2017. She has English and Hungarian publications on the topics of sexual life stories, bisexuality, and intimate partnership violence in the Central-Eastern European context. She taught Gender Studies classes, volunteered in LGBTQ support services, and participated in international research projects on gender, domestic violence, children's and elderly care.

Elena Likhomanova

Feminism and LGBTQIAP in Russia: sociopolitical and scientific discourse

Gender is a part of every aspect of our lives: economic, familial, sexual, educational or class. Thereby, today gender nonconformity and feminism become more important. In the Russian Federation, there are 2 federal laws marginalising the LGBTQIAP community: the law on "prohibition of homosexuality propaganda" and the law protecting children from "information that is harmful to their health". Despite the fact that that gender (or sexual) orientation and gender identity (and gender expression) are different phenomena, the confusion of these concepts exists even at the legislation level. For example, in 2011, absolute majority of voters in the Kostroma region voted in favor of prohibiting propaganda of "homosexuality, bisexuality, transsexualism and pedophilia" among minors. This law pathologizes non-heteronormative sexual orientations and gender identities (which contradicts modern scientific data), and creates a frightening image of LGBTQIA+ people by listing them among pedophiles.

Unfortunately, intolerance towards LGBT+ exists on the academic level. For example, in 2015, a MSU professor, Dr. Matveeva,

presented the expert conclusion on printed and video material of the community "Children-404", providing support and psychological help to non-heteronormal adolescents. It sparked a stormy discussion: Russian psychologists prepared a petition asking for this conclusion to be considered unsatisfactory "from a professional psychological community point of view" and recognize it as violating the Russian Psychological Society Code of Ethics, the Convention for the Protection of Human Rights and Fundamental Freedoms, the Convention on the Rights of the Child, ICD-10.

Next topic is the Russian feminist discourse. Recently more feminist spaces and initiative groups started to develop, - for example, "Podruzhestvo", "Eva's Ribs", Femband, RFC "SHE" etc. Therefore, the question arises of who belongs there: transgender people is a major controversy. Next aspect of transgender question in Russian feminism is gender oppression. Feminists who support queer theory believe that the increase in the number of gender identities, as well as the discrepancy between gender identity and gender expression should gradually lead to their deconstruction and, as a result, discrimination against women. Trans-exclusive feminists believe this will only lead to a cementing of gender roles and stereotypes (TERFs also criticize binary transgender people, as trying to appear excessively masculine or feminine in order to look like "Real Women" or "Real Men").

Homosexual and bisexual women are also a crucial force in Russian feminism. As more and more queer women identify as feminists, the gap between lesbian and bisexual feminists and lesbian and bisexual non-feminists also increases. Our society is becoming more aware of domestic violence in lesbian relationships. We can also observe some separatist initiatives, as women become more sexually self-aware, and prefer living with women to living with men.

Therefore, this report is devoted to the interaction between Russian LGBTQIAP and feminist communities, their coexistence in the context of discriminatory laws, as well as the psychological studies

within the destigmatising context of LGBT+ groups, psychological and feminist projects, aimed at creation of safe space.

Elena Likhomanova, Moscow State University, Faculty of Psychology. I am a queer person, intersectional feminist, neuropsychologist and gender researcher, and founder of the feminist project «Podruzhestvo: a safe space».

Lara Özlen

Identity Politics and Solidarity Practices of Les-Bi Women in İstanbul

Focusing on people who identify themselves as lesbians or bisexuals in İstanbul, this research aims to explore woman-to-woman socialization processes and their possible relations with identity-making, solidarity in predominantly heterosexual set ups, and politics. I divide my research into two main tracks related to women's socialization: physical /public spaces that women frequent (bars) and digital/virtual spaces (dating applications). Thus, I aimed to explore commonalities and differences between lesbian-bisexual socialization mediums in order to have a wider perspective on relationships established among these spaces, and their effects on politics.

“Being in the LGBTI+ scene,” and “hanging out” means drinking, flirting, dancing that can be a part of long/ short term dating or friendly encounters. Socialization in LGBTI+ friendly spaces is a significant part of LGBTI+ culture, because they create relatively “safe spaces” within larger heteronormative structures. I aimed to explore whether these socializations may also function as a part of processes of creation of community and building of solidarity.

Throughout my research on les-bi socialization via applications and

bars, I delve more into the effect of “socializations” on building forms of solidarity through different lesbian-bisexual subjects. How can such mediums be intertwined on the common ground of lesbian-bisexual socializations? How may they affect les-bi women’s feelings of belonging to a community? In which aspects people perceive dynamics of getting together with “people like you” as political? How are personal intimacies related to broader characteristics of lesbian-bisexual politics? One of the aims of this research is to address the gap of lesbian-bisexual literature in Turkey, and explore les-bi visibility in LGBTI+ community in Istanbul.

Bio

I graduated from İstanbul Bilgi University's FTV department and currently doing my MA at İstanbul Sabanci University in Cultural Studies. My research interests include queer, gender, and memory studies. The thesis I am still working on aims to focus on woman-to-woman socialization and the possible relations between intimate relationships and the dynamics of solidarity and politics.

Catrinel Dunca

The Personal and the Political: From India to Romania, with Queerly Love

Theorising queer and LGBTQI+ lives and modes of being, and consequently utopias we envisage and the activism we engage in towards these bears the marks of the many preceding discourses, at the same time as being contingent upon the politics of the times. Queer (and) feminist discourses become more than tools to achieve political ends. They become moments of self-awareness in shaping the goals of our resistance and struggle; recurrent attempts to make sense of and to ‘matter’ the interstices of identities, forms of

relationality, forms of re/presentation which have either remained culturally obscured, or have been figured as abnormal, unnatural, 'sickly'.

The paper will use as a starting point two cultural products from two vastly different socio-economic, political and cultural contexts: Deepa Mehta's film *Fire* (1995) and Tudor Giurgiu's film *Legaturi Bolnavicioase* (2006). Through a theoretical framework which nuances Judith Butler's discussions of performativity and of the process of subjection/subjectivation, and draws on Teresa de Lauretis' playful approach to the narrative constructed by psychoanalysis, the paper will attempt multiple parallel readings of the two films, to explore ways in which they 'matter' at different stages of queer feminist theorising and activism.

Rather than reading the two cultural products in themselves, the paper will attempt to place the readings within the broader context of the queer and LGBTQI+ movements taking place in India and Romania, to do a potted history of the uncomfortable yet productive relationship between what often raises suspicion as 'Western theoretical imports' and specific local contexts, complicated by gender, caste, class etc. This is also an attempt, at a point where the Queer and LGBTQI+ movements need more than ever to make allies, both in theorising and activism, within and across borders, to share what has been a difficult yet incredible journey, still ongoing, of making sure that the movement in India remains dynamic and open to challenge from Dalit, rural, workers' voices etc. To return to the metaphor of the film, that is to ask, what does it mean that Radha and Sita continuously re-orient their knowledge in the context of Gandhian thought and of the Ramayana, while Alex and Kiki appeal to foreign literature to articulate 'the love that dare not speak its name' (Narain and Bhan, 2004)? How does this reflect a broader political commitment and challenge to heteropatriarchal institutions, which do not restrict themselves to the boundaries of the private (understood as identity and sexual practice), but take into account the

overarching implications to processes of knowledge making, and making lives ‘matter’ in all their intersecting dimensions?

Catrinel Dunca is a queer feminist researcher and occasional writer, who currently works with the Research and Training Unit of the Human Development and Research Centre, Ahmedabad, and teaches Critical Theory, Gender Studies and other motley things at the MA level at St. Xavier’s College, Ahmedabad. Her PhD, *Beyond Heteronormativity: The Shaping of the Lesbian Ethos in India between the 1990s and 2009*, brought together her dreams of ‘justice as love’ and brought her into contact with queer feminist groups across India. Her research continues in the areas of queer theory, psychoanalysis, popular fiction, social justice etc.

Andreas Athanasiades

Queer Desire as a Political Force: the Gay Pride Parade in Cyprus and the Queering of Cypriot Culture

In May 2014 the first ever Gay Pride Parade was held with tremendous success in Cyprus, a society that is still by-and-large very conservative. At the same time, in an adjacent street, the powerhouse that is the Greek Orthodox Church, organised a counter-parade comprising of far-right individuals, nuns and priests which, both in terms of numbers and influence, failed spectacularly. This paradox spurred a wave of analyses and examination of the way in which Cypriot society and culture seem to be changing -engaged as it would seem in a queering process- as well as on issues such as gay activism and civil partnership. My proposed presentation analyses the ways in which the Parade’s expressed queer desire and the participants’ performativity, gesture towards a significant socio-political change in Cyprus. This analysis is largely based on Deleuze and Guattari’s notion of desire as a machine that generates

reality, as I approach the Parade's "queerness" as an expression of Cypriot society's polyvalent socio-political manifestations which intentionally include the disenfranchised and provide new answers to questions of belonging. It is ultimately argued that, the way in which performative imagination seems to be able to generate reality, gestures towards a better understanding of the weak points of a dominant structure, becoming thus much more influential than the way in which Michel Foucault understands the notion of "power". In other words, that the participants' actions, choices and played-out desires lead to a final, dual performance that is the Parade and the counter-parade on the "stage" that is Cyprus. The Parade's cultural performativity then, can be read as a site of vital performances, a kind of Bakhtinian carnivalesque that can lead to an understanding of a new socio-political identity which entails hope for the future. Thus, the dynamics of non-heteronormative sexual identities in Cyprus and their political potentials are explored vis-à-vis their capacity to interrogate hegemonic discourses, all of which gestures towards the queering of Cypriot culture.

Andreas received his BA in English Language and Literature from the University of Cyprus, graduating with excellence in 2003. A year later he completed his MA at the University of Leeds, graduating with Merit. He is currently an early career scholar teaching at the University of Cyprus, having completed his PhD in English Literature and Comparative Cultural Studies at the University of Cyprus in 2013 on a full scholarship from the Government of Cyprus, with his PhD dissertation exploring socio-political connotations of desire and sexuality in the works of Hanif Kureishi. He has published articles and book chapters on Islamic fundamentalism, desire, and identity in the *Journal of Postcolonial Writing* and *Indi@Logs* among others. His academic interests include postcolonialism, desire and sexuality, memory, life writing, and cinematic studies.

Myrto Tsilimpounidi

Queering Bratislava: On borders, otherness and public space

"Arriving at each new city, the traveler finds again a past of his that he did not know he had: the foreignness of what you no longer are or no longer possess lies in wait for you in foreign, unpossessed places." (Italo Calvino, *Invisible cities*)

The presentation is based on personal diaries, urban walks and visual material collected in Bratislava during the last 14 months. It involves maneuvering the borders of insider and outsider to the city, as the researcher arrived for a fellowship from the UK in Slovak academia but also to the everyday Bratislavian realities. It follows the multiple layers of an urban fabric that is stereotypically characterised as 'post-socialist', yet in essence it is subject to ongoing transitions – much like the notion of being queer. What can we learn from queer theory in relation to post-socialist urban theory? What are the methodological advancements that derive from a queer approach on research? In this light the presentation breaks the (usually) logocentric academic discourse as it engages with the premises of visual sociology. Using visual material from Bratislava focusing on urban inscriptions (street art, urban interventions) it opens up a discussion about the changes in the city and the struggles of different groups.

Dr. Myrto Tsilimpounidi is a social researcher and photographer. Her research focuses on the interface between urbanism, culture, and innovative methodologies. She is the author of *Sociology of Crisis: Visualising Urban Austerity* (Routledge, 2017) and the editor of *Remapping Crisis: A Guide to Athens* (Zero Books, 2014) and *Street*

Art & Graffiti: Reading, Writing & Representing the City (Routledge, 2017). Myrto is the co-director of Ministry of Untold Stories and a Marie Curie Fellow at the Institute for Sociology of the Slovak Academy of Sciences.

Anna Carastathis

Intersectionality versus racism: syntaxes of oppression in Greece

In the summer and autumn of 2015, I met with activists in Athens and Thessaloniki, with the aim of collaboratively producing a conceptual mapping of LGBTQ social movement discourses. My point of entry was the use and signification of “racism” in LGBTQ discourses (and more generally in common parlance in Greek) as a superordinate or “umbrella” concept that includes “homophobic” and “transphobic” but also “misogynist,” “ageist,” “ableist,” and class- or status-based prejudice, discrimination, and oppression, in addition to that, of course, based on “race” or “ethnicity.” As a political theorist whose work over the past decade has focused on the concept of intersectionality, its origins in US Black feminist thought, and its transnational travel beyond the Anglo-American context in which it originated, I wanted to examine how this use of “racism” relates to the concept of “intersectionality” [in Greek, translated as *διαθεματικότητα*] which is now emergent in the Greek social movement context, in particular in LGBTQ and feminist discourses, yet which has not been engaged by academics, neither in the nascent and struggling field of gender studies, nor in legal theory.

Intersectionality constitutes a framework for theorising relations between various systems of oppression (which produce privileges), that are experienced simultaneously but are falsely separated from one another by means of complex hegemonic and counterhegemonic discursive processes. To the extent that intersectionality—as it is

generally understood, as a multi-axial theory of oppression—seems to presuppose the irreducibility of multiple “axes” of oppression to each other, it seemed to me that the deployment of this concept was in tension with the more commonplace use of “racism” as a superordinate concept. I had reservations about the possible appropriation of the word “racism” and the specific experiences which it describes. The etymology of the word seems to legitimise the narrow use of the term to refer to oppressions that target groups on the basis of “race”—or, more correctly, which racialise their targets in order to legitimise racism. Therefore, the use of “racism” to refer to oppressions targeting LGBTQ people who are part of the dominant ethno-racial group (in this case, Greek Orthodox Christians with the privilege of citizenship) could be seen as appropriative. Still, I wanted to inquire after the forms of “knowledge” this apparent “ignorance” reveals; in particular, whether the universal use of the term “racism” without “race” as its ontological anchor was rooted in particular prereflective or theorised perceptions about the relationship of various forms of oppression to each other.

How do LGBTQ activists define the referential scope and semantic contents of these concepts, based on what knowledges grounded in lived experiences, and on what kinds of social movement strategies? How do these concepts and their theoretical underpinnings reflect or direct activists’ political resistance to the widespread violence that they identify within and on the borders of Greek society? Do they enable coalition-building with other minoritised groups targeted by institutional and interpersonal “racism”? In approaching these questions, I wanted to trace the ways in which my interlocutors produce theories, through which social conditions of racist, heteronormative, and gendered power are made visible, are explained, and are contested—conditions that they identify with the institutions—“nation, religion, and family”—that make up what they termed the “trptych” or the “syntax of power.” What emerged in my conversations with activists were vivid accounts of the atmospheric

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violence facing LGBTQ people in Greece, its institutional and interpersonal manifestations, both banal and extreme. Indeed, many activists defined violence as the quintessence of oppression as such, and as what links various systems or forms of oppression—or, “racisms”—to one another. In the paper on which this proposed presentation is based, I draw on these conversations to answer not only the questions with which I set out, but, perhaps more importantly, those that my interlocutors generated, which concern, ultimately, the unlivability of queer and trans lives in Greek nationalised space—the violence LGBTQ people face and resist, particularly at the intersections of youth, poverty, disability, rurality, racialisation, criminalisation, and patriarchy.

Dr. Anna Carastathis completed her M.Sc. in Gender Studies at the University of the Aegean and her Ph.D. in political philosophy at McGill University, and has held research and teaching positions in various universities in the United States and Canada. She is the author of *Intersectionality: Origins, Contestations, Horizons* (University of Nebraska Press, 2016). Her current research examines the crises produced by the war on migration as it articulates austerity capitalism, focusing on the Aegean sea crossing in the eastern Mediterranean. She is a founding member of Feminist Researchers Across and Against Borders.

Alyosxa Tudor

***Postmigrant Desires: Opposing Romanian
'Cross-Border-Nationalism', Queering the Longing for
Belonging***

This paper looks at conceptualisations of postmigrant desires and the contradictions that are created through 'cross-border-nationalism' on the one hand and the longing for belonging of migratised subjects on the other. Through an examination of theories on transing and belonging and illustrated by discursive examples from transgender communities and Romanian migrant communities, I call for a conceptualisation of entangled power relations that does not rely on fixed, pre-established categories but defines subjectivity through risk in political struggle. The paper explores potentials and limits of going beyond 'the national' and 'gender' and intervenes in forms of minority nationalism that reproduce racism, sexism, heteronormativity and gender binary as the norm of European national belonging.

Opposing 'cross-border-nationalism', a form of nationalism often established in migrant communities that constructs the diaspora as a nationalist extension of the homeland, I argue that the 'post' in 'postmigrant' offers a way of thinking Europe as a diasporic space (Brah 1996), where migration and transit is the norm and not the exception. It is a change of perspective that does not persist in the 'eternal' condition of having just arrived but conceptualises migrations as a condition of persistence and therefore intervenes in hegemonic nationalist/racist understandings of time, movement, staying and belonging.

My intervention is built on the claim that neither crossing borders nor transing or queering gender and sexuality is a guarantee for transgressive politics. While the term 'postmigrant' offers the possibility of transing diaspora and seeing kinship beyond national origins, we must problematise the hierarchy the 'post' risks

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reproducing. Who are those who have just arrived, who are those who have never left? For how long does one stay an Eastern European migrant in the West and when does one begin to inhabit Western privilege? How can I relate my self-narrative as a queer-feminist migrant kid who grew up in a Romanian and German family in Germany with anti-nationalist, anti-racist, queer-feminist politics that do not romanticise neither the diaspora nor the homeland? When I long for hearing Romanian being spoken by strangers passing by in the streets of Western metropolis, how can I make sense of the potential difference in our positions? In my head the conserved intellectual Romanian of the 1970s that my parents brought to Germany, on my tongue nothing like a shameful German accent. How do possibilities of geographic and national belonging, class, migration, racialisation, gender and sexuality divide us, in the streets, and here at the conference, and how do we endure the contradictions in struggles for radical social transformation?

Round table hosts

Alice Iancu is a Lecturer in Political Science at Hyperion University, Bucharest and associate teacher at the National School of Political and Administrative Sciences, Department of International Relations, Bucharest. My initial main focus of research and most of my published work focuses on feminist responses to austerity and poverty in a Romanian context. However in recent years I have been engaging more with research on reproductive rights, heteronormativity in a Romanian context and intersectional theorizing. The tensions and opportunities arising from negotiating academia and activist engagement have been an undercurrent of my work and thought.

Bogdan Popa is a Lecturer in Gender Studies, University of Cambridge, UK. He is a member of the collective Abolition. His next book is titled *Sexual Horror and the Invention of a New Future*. Turning to the work of queer feminist and critical race theorists ranging from W.E.B. Du Bois to Lauren Berlant, Fred Moten and Sara Ahmed, it shows that horror became a key mechanism to produce a global history of white heteronormativity. In illuminating that whiteness produces distinct historical types of sexual monsters, the book draws on various archives from early American documents and political theory to film studies and the history of socialism.

Dr Alyosxa Tudor is a Lecturer in Gender Studies at the Centre for Gender Studies at SOAS, University of London. Their work connects trans and queer feminist, transnational feminist and postcolonial theories and epistemologies. Alyosxa's main research interest lies in analysing (knowledge productions on) migrations, diasporas and borders in relation to critiques of Eurocentrism and to processes of gendering and racialisation. In the past, Alyosxa was a LSE Fellow in Transnational Gender Studies and a Senior Teaching Fellow at the Centre for Gender Studies, SOAS.

Organizers

Ramona Dima (University of Bucharest)

With an educational background in Literature and Communication Studies, I am currently a PhD candidate at the Faculty of Journalism and Communication Studies. My research subject revolves around queer cultural products in Romania, the approach being placed at the intersection of cultural, literary and media studies from a queer and feminist theory perspective. In 2014, I started to work together with my life partner, Simona Dumitriu. We have also collaborated in collective performances and installations at Platforma space in Bucharest and wrote *Bahlui Arcadia* for Tranzit Iași and *Hortus Conclusus* and *The Body Elastic* for Museums Quartier Wien.

Simona Dumitriu was part of the artist collective which coordinated (2011-2015) Platforma project space in Bucharest. She taught (2009-2013) graduate and post-graduate courses of contemporary photography at the National University of the Arts Bucharest. She is now an independent curator, writer and organizer. With her life partner, Ramona Dima, started in 2014 the artist duo Simona&Ramona (aka Claude&Dersch). Since 2015 she is a member of *Local Goddesses*, an informal group of women* artists. Since 2016 *Local Goddesses* have started FemCAV, a program dedicated to exhibiting multimedia and performance projects made by women*, hosted by CAV Multimedia Center (a space belonging to the Artists Union Bucharest).

www.simonaramona.wordpress.com

www.poetrybody.wordpress.com

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